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HUMANIZING CITIES: THE IMPACT OF BUILT ENVIRONMENT ON THE HUMAN STATE OF MIND

A Thesis submitted to the Council of the College of City and Regional Planning – University of Duhok as a partial fulfilment of the Requirement for the Degree of Master of Science in Spatial Planning

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Dedication

This thesis is dedicated to my beloved parents, whose unwavering support and belief in the power of knowledge have been my greatest inspiration.

I also dedicate this work to my family and friends, whose persistent encouragement has been a constant source of strength and motivation.

Lastly, this work is for everyone passionate about education and eager to explore and build upon this research

May this work be an inspiration to recognize that cities and environments must be thoughtfully crafted with Humans at the heart of every decision.

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ABSTRACT

This research originated from a deep interest in understanding the correlation between humans and their surroundings. Urban design aspects that affect people's state of mind were investigated, particularly focusing on the urban built environments in Duhok City. The study tackled the growing concern globally that human mental well-being has not been given enough attention during city development efforts in many parts of the world nowadays.

The rapid expansion of cities due to hasty population growth and rural-urban migration has resulted in a lack of human-centric approaches in the design of the physical environment, particularly concerning the mental well-being of citizens. This research is crucial as it explores how certain built environment elements can improve residents' emotional and perceptual experiences, making cities more livable and emotionally rich.

The study's main objectives were to identify the key physical elements within urban spaces that positively impact people's emotional and perceptual states to enhance quality of life. A combination of insights was gathered from architecture, urban planning, and environmental psychology, highlighting a need for a multidisciplinary approach to meet the goals and objectives of the research.

Furthermore, findings highlighted a significant correlation between enhanced emotional well-being in positively perceived urban environments, particularly in spaces that integrated historical, natural, and narrative elements. This study highlighted the significance of designing environments with the human mental state in mind, by offering practical guidelines and recommendations for urban planners, architects, and policymakers.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Full Term
SLOAP	Space Left Over After Planning
IDP	Internally Displaced People
KRG	Kurdistan Regional Government
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
UN	United Nations
PANAS	Positive and Negative Affect Schedule
SAM	Self-Assessment Manikin
EEG	Electroencephalogram
AR	Augmented Reality
VR	Virtual Reality

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CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

The movement of nearly half of the world's population to urban environments as their primary habitats indicates major human history changes. This trend is expected to grow, with projections suggesting that urban areas will accommodate 70% of the world's population by 2050. Due to this mass migration to urban environments, many challenges have been raised in urban design and planning, particularly in creating spaces that promote healthy daily living. Hence, the contemporary urban settings and rapid growth of urbanization have led to an increased focus on the need for human-centered urban design as (UnitedNationsSDGs, 2015).

Furthermore, UNESCO has highlighted a concerning trend in the contemporary design of built environments, noticing a shift away from human-centric approaches that have become less conducive to human well-being (Unesco, 2016). This change has corresponded with a rise in non-communicable diseases like obesity and diabetes, alongside psychological conditions such as stress and depression (WHO, 2023).

Consequently, the United Nations “Working Towards a Better Urban Future” program emphasizes the failure of many cities to consider the human experience within the urban environment design, and their impacts on human well-being. It advocates an urban planning approach that balances the physical, economic, social, and emotional aspects of citizens (Abdel Hamid and Ahmed, 2020, UnitedNationsSDGs, 2015). The significance of this study gained larger insights after the COVID-19 epidemic, which has reinforced the urban space design needs for the physical and mental well-being of city dwellers (Sharifi and Khavarian-Garmsir, 2020). In response to this multifaceted challenge, there is a growing paradigm that advocates the design and development of human-centered cities. Similarly, the “European Landscape Convention” confirms this perspective, recognizing the importance of everyday urban elements in enhancing life quality; through recognizing the value of everyday areas, such as streets, squares, and buildings (Bornioli and Subiza-Pérez, 2023).

Historically, the concept of human-centered design emerged as a response to the 20th-century crisis within built environments and the rise of modernism. Modernism by many traditional analysts was geometrical abstraction imposed on the countries' natural and historical landscapes and their societies, destroying the urban and cultural fabrics of the past (Blake, 1964).

The Kurdistan Region of Iraq has 129 urban centers, with around 84% of its population living in urban areas, and 16% living in rural (KRGStatisticsOffice, 2025). This fact illustrates the mass movement of people which has been and still is taking place, from the rural areas to the main cities. This huge migration happened as a result of factors accumulated during the last few years. The most important factors are the continued movement from rural to urban areas, the dramatic increase in human population, and the availability of public services in the metropolitans while lacking in rural areas (khaleel Ismael and Ngah, 2010).

The Kurdistan region is currently undergoing rapid changes and developments in various ways. The economy is growing, and the population is rising. People and their social behaviors are influenced by these advancements; particularly in small and medium-sized cities, for instance, Duhok City (Khoshnaw, 2019). In the context of Duhok, urban form and structure have not been considered in examining and evaluating the sustainability of the built environment. There are no rigid guidelines and regulations in urban development plans and strategies in the Kurdistan region to control urban form and structure, which in turn, has led to significant gaps in knowledge (Hajani, 2019).

Urban planning and design in Duhok are predominantly driven by economic motives and rapid expansion with little regard to human-centric aspects. This approach has resulted in a random urban environment that neglects crucial human dimensions, affecting the quality of life of residents. This research will investigate the complex relationship between urban design and human experience in Duhok City. It aims to explore how specific urban environments influence residents' perceptions as well as their emotional experiences.

1.1. Research Problem

- **Modernism & Cultural Identity Loss:** Modernist urban design obliterated cultural identity and shifted away from human-centered design, leading to segregation and diminished social life.
- **Rapid Urbanization:** Uncontrolled urban growth threatens heritage, green spaces, and urban livability, causing challenges in creating human-centered built environments.

1.2. Aim of Research

The research attempts to reach the following Aims:

- Aligning with the Sustainable development goals of SDG 11 & 15 by Creating inclusive, resilient, green Urban Environments SDG 4 & 17, integrating urban planning and psychology for interdisciplinary knowledge, and finally SDG 3 for Promoting mental well-being.
- Answering the Global advocacy by the United Nations and UNESCO for more humanized city approaches, that integrate social, psychological, and physical factors that are important for human well-being in the planning strategies.

1.3. Research Questions

The current study attempts to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the Physical elements of urban design that influence the human state of mind?
2. How does the urban built environment impact human emotions and perception of Duhok City Residents?
3. How does human-environmental interaction contribute to humanizing urban environments?

1.4. Research Objectives

This study attempts to achieve the following Objectives:

1. To identify key physical elements in urban design that affect perceptual and emotional experiences.
2. To investigate the influence of the urban built environment on the emotional and perceptual experience of Duhok City's residents.
3. To explore the dynamic interplay between humans and their environment in enhancing the humanistic quality of the urban environments in Duhok.

1.5. Significance of the research

This study explores the complex human-environmental relations between physical environments and human experience, utilizing an interdisciplinary approach that combines the areas of urban design, planning, and psychology. This falls within the domain of environmental psychology, which highlights the significance of this study in understanding how urban surroundings influence human experiences. This thesis came from an initial interest in the exploration of how human beings fit into the urban environment; and more specifically, how architects and planners play a role in the design and maintenance of the cities' evolving systems. Nowadays, the focus on sustainability is motivated by the quality of the environment, public health, and people's well-being.

Emphasizing the importance of improving public life quality and recognizing humans as central to any development. Through a cross-disciplinary research effort that includes urban design, planning, and environmental psychology to examine how people perceive urban environments and experience them. This involves studying perceptions and emotions to determine the most human-friendly elements in design. The aim is to generate guidelines and recommendations to design better urban environments, thereby supporting the fabric of city life. This research emphasizes the importance of creating more human-friendly urban settings to enhance the overall quality of life in response to UNESCO's approach and the global decline in humanistic qualities in cities. The research supports redesigning urban spaces and creating urban environments that are not only effective but also support the overall well-being of the citizens. Combining objective scientific approaches with subjective measures to improve the connection between people and their urban surroundings leads to a more compassionate and inclusive urban future.

1.6. Research Structure

The research is divided into six chapters as shown in Figure 1, to provide a systematic and comprehensive explanation of the study as follows:

➤ Chapter One: Introduction

The first chapter introduces the research, primarily setting the groundwork for the study by identifying the research problem and defining the research questions and objectives. It concludes by highlighting the significance of the study and its contribution to academic and practical knowledge.

➤ **Chapter Two: Research Background**

The background chapter provides the context for the research, outlining the key definitions and concepts relevant to the study to establish a foundational understanding.

➤ **Chapter Three: Literature Review**

The literature review builds on the previous chapter and further delves into the historical evolution of the human-centered design concept. It highlights the key aspects and methods utilized in planning and urban design to address and implement this concept. The second half investigates deeper into similar research examples, conclusions, and contributions to the field. Subsequently, the study gap and variables are identified.

➤ **Chapter Four: Research Methodology**

This chapter outlines the research methodology, including research design, tools, and methods for data collection and analysis. It further describes the case study area, sampling methods, and data analysis techniques utilized in the research.

➤ **Chapter Five: Results and Discussion**

This chapter presents the results and interprets the findings of the study. This includes the raw data obtained from questionnaires and their visualization into themes, graphs, tables, and other visual tools to represent the findings. The results are discussed and compared to the results of similar studies in existing literature.

➤ **Chapter Six: Conclusion and Recommendations**

The final chapter summarizes key results and findings and deliberates their implication in urban design and planning. It offers recommendations for future research and practical implications based on the outcomes of the study.

Figure 1 The Structure of the research, created by the Researcher

CHAPTER TWO

RESEARCH BACKGROUND

2. Main concepts and definitions

The main concepts and definitions of the research refer to the key terms related to the built environment and human state of mind.

2.1. Definitions related to the research

- **Humanizing city:** a key term in the study that refers to the practice of designing urban environments that prioritize human needs. Thereby enhancing the overall quality of urban life. This concept reflects an approach to designing urban environments that aims to rehumanize urban spaces that are physically appealing, emotionally sustaining, and inclusive. This concept aligns with the global sustainable development goals (Yang et al., 2016; Gehl, 2010; UNESCO, 2016).
- **Built environment:** This term refers to the man-made and natural settings which people daily interact with. As a collaboration of multiple disciplines, including interior design, architecture, urban design, and urban planning. The built environment includes buildings, infrastructures, and urban spaces. it plays an important role in shaping the human experience that shapes their physical and mental well-being that is a result of human-environment interaction (Roberts & Greed, 2014, Designing Buildings, 2020, Gomes, 2021).
- **Urban Design's perceptual dimension:** It is one of the dimensions utilized in urban design, it focuses on how people perceive and experience the built environments. Particularly referring to the perception and experience of "Place" (Gregorowicz-Kipszak, 2015).

The key concepts involved in urban design's perceptual dimensions are:

- **Place Identity:** it is where the design of the place reflects the identity of the community (Lynch, 1964).
- **Sense of Place:** it refers to the emotional and psychological attachment to certain places (Tuan, 1977).
- **Placelessness:** it is the reflection of places that lack unique characteristics, which can lead to disconnection (Relph, 1976).

- Environmental perception: It is the study of how people perceive and respond to their environment through the main five senses. It further extends to include the cognitive process that humans experience when interacting with their surroundings, through perceiving, sensing, interpreting, and evaluating, which is influenced by personal and cultural backgrounds (Carmona, 2021).
- Human experience: it can be defined as the collective response to human-environment interactions (Noguchi, Lan, Chowdhury, & Yang, 2022).
- Environmental psychology: It is a multidimensional discipline that investigates the interactions between people and their surroundings, including both built and natural environments (Ittelson et al., 1974).

2.2. The Concept of Built Environment and Human Interaction

The built environment can be understood as a human-made environment. Where humans interact daily, such as in buildings, infrastructure, and open spaces. It covers both natural and man-made elements that make up the physical surroundings (Lopez, 2012). The built environment plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' physical and mental well-being, affecting their self-transcendence journey (Sosteric, 2019). The built environment is the result of the collaboration of multiple disciplines, including interior design, architecture, urban design, and urban planning, as shown in Figure 2. This specific method arises from the increasing complexities of design procedures, which calls for considering a range of scales, materials, technologies, and different specifications. (Roberts and Greed, 2014).

Figure 2 Erickson, B & Lloydjones, T 2001, *Approaching Urban Design. The Design Process*, Taylor & Francis. (Roberts & Greed, 2014)

Erickson and Lloydjones developed a model that the activity of design “attempts to make the future better than the present this involves a planned change in the material world”.

In particular, Lawson argues that three-dimensional and environmental design “generate objects or places which may have a major impact on the quality of life of many people” (Roberts and Greed, 2014). The matrix as shown in Figure 3 categorizes design activities by scale, ranging from smaller to larger, and by different aspects of the built environment.

It is organized into four rows: Political Unit, Built Form, Urban Space, and Design Activity. Each column represents a different scale, beginning with the individual and extending to the government on the political scale, and from room to metropolitan region on the built form and urban space scales.

Figure 3 scale of Design activity in the built environment (Roberts & Greed, 2014)

The COVID-19 pandemic period has been the opportunity to re-evaluate the built environments, specifically the urban open spaces which became a priority, with an emphasis on adapting these areas to better enhance public needs and improve environmental sustainability. Gomes (2021) highlights this period as a critical opportunity for collaborative efforts in urban planning to create more responsive, inclusive, and eco-friendly public spaces. The aim is to redesign parks, squares, and streets to support diverse activities, social interactions, and community well-being while minimizing environmental impacts. The present time emerges as an opportunity to change the planning paradigm (Gomes, 2021). The call by Gomes (2021) for a paradigm shift in planning and design practices reflects a broader movement toward creating more humanized environments. This approach acknowledges the complex role of urban open spaces in contributing to the overall health and sustainability of cities.

2.2.1. Built environment and Urban space design

Urban space is all the spaces between buildings in towns and other localities (Krier and Rowe, 1979) It is an outdoor space defined as an exterior space in architecture and architecture without a roof (Ashihara, 1981) referring to the physical spaces within a city that are used by the public and can include courtyards, streets, squares, and quarters. These spaces represent the public realm where most of the social interaction within a city occurs. their design is important for the functionality, aesthetics, and social life of urban areas (Marcus and Francis, 1997).

Urban space is created and defined by buildings that constitute boundaries between internal and external space. It is the “void” between buildings for outdoor activities and for movement, to take in public life in the city. It facilitates the coming together of people in other terms, the social dimension, which is the essence of the ‘urban’ in a cultural sense (Carmona and Tiesdell, 2007). The concept of Modern architecture and urbanism has overturned all the heritage of urban spaces (squares and streets) and their design for other spaces that some called (space left over after planning) SLOAP is an unbuilt space with no relationship with the built environment, however in Postmodern architecture era urban spaces status stayed at its modern conception despite of the rationalists urge, led principally by Robert and Leon Krier, to revive the urban spaces heritage as the sole spaces for public life (Bada, 2012).

2.2.2. Concept of space and place

The concept of space, deeply examined across various disciplines like architecture, psychology, and sociology, is a multifaceted entity that intertwines physical, psychological, and social aspects. Derived from the Latin 'spatium', meaning distance or void, space in its essence is both a physical and abstract phenomenon (Goetz and Nancy, 2001). In contrast, the notion of place is imbued with human experiences, emotions, and memories, transforming mere spaces into meaningful locations.

While space refers to the physical environment, place is about the emotional and social connections that people form with it. It is seen as a location filled with a sense of belonging, purpose, and identity, where social interactions and cultural norms are expressed. This distinction between space and place underscores the importance of human perception, emotion, and social interaction in shaping our understanding of the physical world.

2.2.3. Physical and Perceptual Space

Space has been categorized by Architects and planners into physical and perceptual, forming a connection between people and their surrounding environment. Physical space is tangible and measurable. It is the actual, quantifiable area that is enclosed within the structural boundaries.

Physical space measurement is objective, and it is a critical component in architecture and planning, which is evaluated by layout, size, and functionality. On the other hand, there is a Perceptual space, which is the subjective experience; it is shaped by sensory perceptions and transcends the physical boundaries influenced by light, color, texture, and scale (Ching, 2023). Perceptual space is concerned with how an individual interprets its volume and character beyond the literal physical boundaries. This experiential aspect is difficult to quantify while equally important in the designing process because it has a direct effect on the human state of mind (Pallasmaa, 2024).

Personal experiences of perceptual space are the meaning base that built and natural environments have for people (Relph, 1976). Shields suggests that our relationship with space goes beyond mere perception; it is where we live, express ourselves, and form emotional connections. When space is experienced deeply, integrating with our lives and identities (Shields, 2023). Figure 4 highlights the dual nature of space. Physical space provides the measurable framework essential for design, whereas perceptual space brings emotional depth.

Figure 4 Physical Vs. Perceptual space by Researcher constructed: from literature

This dichotomy emphasizes the importance of considering both the concrete and sensory aspects, recognizing that spaces are not only built but also lived and felt.

2.3. Urban Design Dimensions

The term ‘urban design’ was coined in North America in the late 1950’s replacing the term ‘civic design’ that focused largely on the siting of civic buildings and their relation to open spaces. Urban design deals with the quality of the urban space, both physical and sociocultural, and how to make places for people to enjoy and use (Gregorowicz-Kipszak, 2015).

The theoretical and professional aim of urban design is to build connections between people and their built environment, therefore, it derives its theories from diverse academic anthropology, political and economic science, and art fields such as sociology, psychology, urban studies, urban geography, (Carmona, 2014, Krieger and Saunders, 2009). Urban design also involves a set of multiple professions, such as architecture, landscape architecture, spatial planning, urban management, and environmental protection (Carmona and Tiesdell, 2007). The dimensions of urban design include morphological, social, perceptual, visual, and temporal aspects, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Dimensions of Urban Design, Source: (urbandesignlab, 2022)

Among these dimensions, the perceptual dimension holds particular importance in understanding and shaping the urban environment (Carmona, 2021).

2.3.1. The Perceptual Dimension

The perceptual Dimension of urban design refers to the perception and experience human creates in a specific “place”, It is the human awareness and appreciation of the surrounding environment. Human experience fundamentally depends on how we interact with the world as embodied agents. The concept of the users' experience in an urban environment includes emotional, perceptual, and cognitive interactions. Perceiving and interpreting built environment are based on factors such as sensory stimuli, cultural influences, and individual background (Burns, 2000).

The perceptual dimension is involved in our ability to gather, organize, and make sense of the information we perceive from the surrounding environment. where the concept of a “sense of place” is generated. It is the outcome of the perceived environment, of how humans can create a sense of a specific place in their minds. This sense is generated in places for their uniqueness, the emotional bonds and attachments developed by humans, or particular experiences people have with their surrounding environment, where this process is called environmental perception.

2.3.2. Environmental Perception

Environmental perception is the study of how people understand and interact with their surroundings, through human senses like vision, hearing, smell, and touch. This field goes beyond mere sensory input if cognitive processes are included such as thinking, feeling, interpreting, and evaluating, which are influenced by social and cultural background.

Since its initiation in the 1960s, Environmental perception gradually evolved into an interdisciplinary area of study, that focuses on how people visualize their environment and encompasses the symbolism and meaning found in built environments, as well as the experiences they provoke. The connection between humans and the environment is bidirectional, meaning we are shaped by our surroundings just as we shape them (Carmona, 2021).

Sensation occurs when our sensory organs pick up external stimuli like light or sound. Perception is the next step, where the brain processes and interprets these signals, constructing a meaningful picture of the environment (Ujang and Sciences, 2012). According to J Douglas Porteous (1997), the most critical sense for interacting with our environment is vision.

Visual perception is a complex process influenced by various factors such as distance, color, and texture. The visual system allows effective navigation and understanding of the world (Porteous, 1997). Understanding sensation and perception is crucial when focusing on human-centric urban design. It enables the creation of spaces that engage users and enhance their environmental interactions. By integrating principles from environmental psychology, designers can develop vibrant and inviting spaces that improve the quality of life for their inhabitants.

2.4. Human state of mind

The human state of mind includes a range of psychological experiences that happen in the human mind, those experiences include cognition, perception, and emotions.

2.4.1. Perception: Bridging Humans and the Environment

Perception is the process by which individuals collect information from the surrounding environment. It represents the intersection of cognitive process and the real-world (Neisser and reality, 1976). This process progresses in four stages: cognitive, affective, interpretive, and evaluative (Ittelson et al., 1974). Essentially, it involves becoming conscious of a space by gathering information through the human senses (Porteous, 1977).

Perception is primarily visual in evaluating aesthetics or behaviors associated with spatial or environmental stimuli. Visual perception enables an individual to collect, identify, and classify information from a given environment, however, perception is not only shaped by physical space but also by personal factors such as education, cultural background, and past experiences (Gifford, 1997).

Humans tend to make evaluative conscious and unconscious judgments, which shape our perception (Kaplan and Kaplan, 1982). Rapoport stated about the perception of the built environment: “Before elements can be organized into schemata and evaluated, they must be perceived”. Therefore, perception is the most important mechanism linking the environment and people (Rapoport, 1977) as depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Illustrating the Interplay Between Human Experience and the Built Environment: An Interpretive Analysis by the Researcher, Adapted from (Rapoport, 1977)

The importance of perception is understood in the notion of urban design. In this regard, the environmental perception is quite like the term “Experience” which was introduced by Tuan (1977). According to Tuan experience, it is made by a person’s sensation, perception, and conception of space which refers to the human cognition process (Tuan, 1977) as illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7 human cognition process, Source: (Tuan, 1977)

Regarding Lang's suggestion on the cognition process, user perception includes more than a simple intellectual connotation associated with an observed object; moreover, it is related to the cognitive process from its beginning stage. The outcome of the perception-cognition processes will lead to the mental image of an environment (Lang, 1987, Canter).

First, humans gain and collect environmental information, then they regulate them in mind, and finally, they praise and respond to them according to their preferences. Nevertheless, in the process of cognition as highlighted in Figure 8, preferences or cultural differences affect the organization of observed elements in the mind.

Researchers like Lang (1987) and Rapoport (1977) have focused on how people and the built environment affect each other. Initially, studies used basic methods like surveys and observations to gather information. However, advances in science and technology, such as bioinformatics, artificial intelligence, virtual environments (Picon and Ponte, 2003),

and neuroscience (Zeisel, 2006), have introduced new tools and ways of studying this interaction.

Figure 8 Three main steps are Perception, Cognition, and Evaluation (Rapoport, 1977).

These advancements have helped us better understand how architecture and urban design can influence human behavior and vice versa. This area of study, combining insights from neuroscience and architecture, is growing and could change how social scientists, engineers, and architects work in the future (Eberhard, 2009). Human experiences in urban environments, from conscious to unconscious activities, emphasize the subjective perspective and interaction with their environment.

This approach reveals how our perceptions, actions, and feelings within cities shape our existence and contribute to our well-being, emphasizing the importance of designing urban spaces that cater to human needs and preferences aiming to create more responsive and user-centered spaces.

2.4.2. Human experience and emotional response

Human experience can be defined as the collective result of our interactions with the world. The change in our physical environment leads to a transformation in our understanding. It emphasizes the dynamic nature of our existence (Auer, 2022).

Our own experience spreads from conscious experience into semi-conscious and even unconscious mental activity according to the strength of interest and interaction. The living experience, such as seeing, thinking, or doing, is central to understanding the essence of consciousness within the urban environment. Our actions, perceptions, and feelings are not the only events that happen to us; but actively shape and define our being, our essence within the urban context.

This means that our lived experiences in urban spaces contribute to the nature of our existence within those spaces (Smith, 2018). Figure 9 illustrates human experience dimensions within the context of architecture and the built environment. It suggests human experience is multi-faceted, including subjective, social, emotional, physical, and spiritual experiences (Noguchi et al., 2022).

Subjective Experience refers to personal perspectives and internal responses, while Social Experience is collective, communal interactions, and societal norms that occur within space. Spiritual Experience deals with transcendental and religious experiences. Physical Experience includes tangible, sensory interactions between humans and the built environment. Lastly, Feelings and psychological responses are called Emotional Experiences. (Noguchi et al., 2022).

Emotional responses refer to the specific reactions and feelings individuals can experience when the built environment triggers their perception (McClure and Bartuska, 2011), in this sense, every space can be designed to create an opportunity for different activities and experiences.

Figure 9 Human experience, source: (Noguchi, Lan, Chowdhury, & Yang, 2022)

(Mehrabian and Russell, 1974) claims that the primary emotional reactions of humans to any spatial experience are pleasure, arousal, and activation. Human behavior is impacted when all of those emotional reactions are reflected in experiences that lead to satisfaction.

In recent years, research in urban studies has shown an increasing interest in the emotional aspects of humans, even though many professionals have neglected them. As stated by (Ferreira, 2013) the emotional data can help planners and positively inspire in the

decision-making process. According to Zeile et al., the long-term goal is to create a new information layer for planners that allows for a visual representation of measured spatial perception (Zeile et al., 2015). These visualizations allow decisions regarding human behavior in an urban environment, enabling a new human-centered approach to planning procedures.

2.5. Human City approach

In the realm of urban development, humanizing the city is defined as designing the city to meet human needs and behaviors, aiming to enhance the quality of life for all inhabitants.(Yang et al., 2016). In literature there are various terms used, such as Human-centered city, Cities for People, and People-friendly Cities, to describe what is referred to as 'human cities'.

The “Human City Institute” has explained it as a place where policies, practices, and initiatives are put into action to support the promising of human endeavors (Gulliver, 2017). Jan Gehl, the architect and urban designer provides a brief explanation of the human city as one that is compact, sustainable, safe, and lively. Within this framework, Gehl emphasizes the importance of carefully designed streets, squares, and open spaces, intending to evoke recreation for users as important elements (Gehl, 2010).

Regarding the evolution of urban development, Nowadays, the re-humanization of cities has become a traveling concept that has been adopted by many cities worldwide (Unesco, 2016). Based on the preceding definitions, A "human city" can be attained by putting its citizens first in the planning process. It is the concept that respects the past through heritage integration, embraces the present with a human-centered design, and shapes a sustainable future for all. Habitat III highlighted the urgent need for this urban development paradigm, aiming to rehumanize urban spaces to increase social cohesion, mitigate segregation, and ensure equitable access to resources (Yang et al., 2016).

The concept of humanizing cities, as advocated by many international organizations, supports urban environments with more accessible, inclusive, and sustainable for their inhabitants. Beginning with the Habitat I conference in Vancouver (1976), there has been a growing recognition of the need for sustainable human settlements, especially in rapidly urbanizing regions. UNESCO's vision emphasizes cities serving their residents, rooted in an ethical approach to urban development. Subsequent conferences, including Habitat II in Istanbul (1996) and Habitat III in Quito (2016), have further underscored the

importance of giving cities a "human face," highlighting the role of cultural diversity, creativity, and architectural heritage in fostering urban success. Modernism with its emphasis on progress and efficiency, often led to the destruction of human-scaled environments, resulting in soulless urban landscapes, displacing vibrant communities, and replacing them with less human-friendly environments (Jacob, 1961).

Modernists have been pivotal in shaping the opposing surrounding urban development, whereas revolutionaries to some, and castrators to others, which have established a new architecture and city design, not only in terms of its physical materiality but also in the way of dealing with the problem of space and how to perceive and build around it (Silva Gouveia et al., 2009). A human-centric city prioritizes citizens' emotional, mental, physical, and economic well-being, considering their psychological aspects and fostering a sense of belonging. This approach integrates heritage, and citizen participation, and enacts policies for a future that respects human dimensions and rights; creating environments that are physically appealing, visually pleasing, and emotionally sustaining while promoting a city's general resilience and well-being (Delgado-Serrano et al., 2019).

The humanization of cities is integral to achieving the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. UNESCO's philosophy is based first and foremost on the ethical premise that cities must serve the people who live in them. (Unesco, 2016). Human cities prioritize people-centered mobility, mixed-use, green areas, and public places, and assure the happiness and well-being of all citizens throughout all stages of the planning process as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 The Components of a Human-centred City Researcher constructed: from literature

2.6. The Psychological Significance of the Human City

The psychological importance of enhancing the implication of a Human-centered approach In urban environments is referred to in many psychological theories and concepts.

They highlight how urban environments can influence mental health, emotional well-being, and the human cognitive process, This can highlight the importance of the existing connection between individuals and their surrounding environments. By integrating psychological insights, Human-environment relationships can become a framework for creating spaces that better enhance human comfort and engagement, further providing a positive emotional experience as referred to in the following concepts.

2.6.1. Rogers Humanism Theory

Humanism is a psychological theory that emphasizes an individual’s inherent drive toward self-actualization. It argues that people have a natural capacity to make decisions about their lives and control their behavior.

Humanism underlines human potential and an individual’s ability to change and rejects the idea of biological determinism. Biological determinism, also known as genetic determinism, is the belief that our genes are primary drivers of who we are and what we do. It suggests that most human physical and mental characteristics are predetermined at

conception by genetic factors, with little or no influence from the environment (Lumen, 2021). One pioneering humanistic theorist was Carl Rogers.

Figure 11 The phenomenal field refers to a person's subjective reality, which includes external objects, people, thoughts (image & behavior), and emotions. The person's motivation acts on their phenomenal field (Lumen, 2021).

An influential humanistic psychologist who developed a personality theory confirms the importance of self-actualizing tendency, which is the highest level of psychological development in shaping the subjective reality of individuals (Orlov, 1992). Rogers believed that humans constantly react to stimuli based on their own subjective experiences and perceptions of the world.

2.6.2. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

To be a human is to be many things. However, beyond genetics, humanity is primarily reflected in our nature as social creatures in physiological and philosophical definitions (Sosteric, 2019). While "to be a human" includes diverse aspects, Abraham Maslow's "hierarchies of needs" offer a structured lens to understand the core motivations driving our social nature.

In 1943, Maslow proposed two distinct hierarchies as depicted in Figure 12, The first "hierarchy of needs" focuses on basic needs like food and shelter, while the second is called "need for transcendence". It addresses higher desires than knowledge and self-actualization, explaining how humans naturally want to feel connected to something bigger than just their daily lives. This connection could be through spirituality, finding meaning in existence, or feeling like they're part of a larger community or universe.

Figure 12 Maslow's hierarchy of needs (Maslow, 1943, Maslow, 1969)

It reflects our innate desire for deeper fulfillment and a sense of belonging beyond the ordinary aspects of life. Maslow argued that fulfilling all these needs is crucial for our well-being (Maslow, 1943).

The human journey towards self-transcendence interconnects with the spaces we inhabit. Understanding this connection, rooted in Maslow's hierarchy of needs (Maslow, 1943) and self-transcendence theory empowers us to design built environments that nurture our highest potential (Ryff and Singer, 2008). In conclusion, the journey towards self-transcendence, as described by Maslow's hierarchy of needs and self-transcendence theory, is linked to the built environments we inhabit. By understanding this connection, we unlock the potential to design spaces that support well-being and enhance human experience.

2.6.3. Social sciences: behavior-environment dynamics

The social and behavioral sciences during the mid-20th century (1949-1969) turned their attention to the relationship between humans and their environments, spurred by intellectual movements showing the importance of "place" and "space." This shift recognized the ecological and social complexities of urban life, fostering a scientific curiosity about how physical environments influence human behavior.

A key figure in this period, B.F. Skinner pioneered the empirical study of observable behavior and its responses to environmental stimuli, underlining the significance of measurable aspects within the field of psychology. Skinner's theory suggests that the design of the built environment can shape behavior, much like an operant conditioning chamber. By incorporating elements like well-lit, inviting seating areas, architects can encourage social interaction, while unpleasant spaces may deter it. Essentially, architectural elements act as cues and consequences that influence behavior within a space (Skinner, 2019). Recent theories in environment behavioral science adopt Post-Modernist and Constructivist views, with interactional, organismic, and transactional theories offering new perspectives on the person-environment relationship, by the work of Altman and Wapner (Wapner, 2000, Moore, 1997).

The intersectional theory suggests that behavior is the result of the individual ongoing interactions with the environment. It emphasizes a bidirectional influence where both the individual and environment actively contribute and shape each other. Organismic theory sees the individual as a proactive entity with intrinsic needs and goals, influencing and being influenced by the environment. Transactional theory proposes that the person and environment are fundamentally inseparable, and any analysis must consider them as a single, integrated unit. It focuses on dynamic and evolving relationships between individuals and their environments. These theories represent different ways of understanding the complex interplay between individuals and their surroundings.

2.6.4. Human City in Neuroscience

Neuroscience is the study of the nervous system, the intricate network of specialized cells that coordinates all of our actions, sensations, and thoughts (allpsychologycareers, 2020). In recent years, neuroscience has significantly influenced architecture and urban planning, leading to the development of "Neuroarchitecture" and "Neurourbanism." Neuroarchitecture is an interdisciplinary field that examines changes in the brain and body due to interactions with the built space, while Neurourbanism combines neuroscience, architecture, urban planning, and sociology to understand the mental health challenges associated with city living.

These fields use tools like brain imaging and eye-tracking to quantify the relationship between individuals and their environments (Cutieru, 2023). The human-centric approach has gained momentum in recent years, there is an incentive to understand how people

perceive and respond to their surroundings. The Centre for Design and Health at the University of Virginia used mobile electroencephalography, or mobile EEG, to explore “what happens in the brain as it navigates the city”, essentially registering the emotions and behaviors triggered by the built environment.

By testing via new tools and urban analysis methods, the research project aims to understand how different urban spaces are conducive to specific activities or the well-being benefit of design elements (Cutieru, 2023). The contribution of neuroscience to environmental psychology has been transformative and helpful to our understanding of human-environmental interaction through advanced tools. These tools have provided detailed insights into how individuals perceive and react to urban spaces. Through measuring brain activity and physiological responses, neuroscience has unveiled the complex processes through which people experience and relate to their surroundings, thus narrowing the gap between technological innovation and the principles of urban design.

2.7. Environmental psychology

Environmental psychology is a multifaceted discipline that explores the dynamic relationship between individuals and their surroundings, both natural and built. It aims to enhance human well-being and enrich the quality of interactions between people and their environments. This field is inherently interdisciplinary, drawing upon methodologies from various research areas to tackle issues of social relevance concerning physical surroundings and human behavior. Originating in the late 1960s, it has been shaped by seminal contributions from researchers like Barker, Hall, Sommer, and Ittelson (Bonaiuto et al., 2010).

This interdisciplinary approach has significantly advanced the field of environmental psychology, which focuses on analyzing how people perceive, conceptualize, and engage with urban environments. Such analyses assist urban designers in creating spaces that promote human well-being. Acknowledging the intricate dynamics that define our interaction with the places we inhabit the

(Bostanci, 2019). The main idea of environmental psychology is understanding perception, cognition, and the way of visual thinking mechanisms of inhabitants and observing their experiences and behaviors in urban spaces. Accordingly, this approach enables urban designers to create positive places and design environmentally and human-friendly public spaces (Bostanci, Bostanci, 2019). The discipline examines both the

effects of the environment on human experiences, behaviors, and well-being, and conversely, how individuals impact their environments (De Groot, 2019). This includes studying environmental behavior, promoting pro-environmental actions, and drawing on insights from psychology, geography, sociology, anthropology, philosophy, neurology, design, architecture, and urban studies. It particularly benefits from research in visual communication, and urban and landscape design, focusing on various spatial levels from personal to global environments (Silva Gouveia et al., 2009, Zeisel, 2006).

The process of perceiving environments begins with sensory inputs, translating external information into personal experiences. This subjective perspective shifts the concept of 'space' into 'place,' emphasizing the unique reality constructed through the interplay of body and mind, encompassing sensing, perceiving, experiencing, and understanding (Piga and Morello, 2015). Environmental perception is crucial for grasping how individuals experience space and the built environment, to deepen our understanding of architectural and environmental experiences (NORBERG-SCHULZ, 1965).

Perception transforms mere physical spaces into meaningful places, engaging all senses and influencing human relations with their surroundings. This interaction is vital for the functionality and value of built environments, fostering social interactions through the design of spaces and their elements. The relationship between users and their environments is seen as a cause-effect interplay, significantly affecting physical and mental health (Lynn Thurber and Phillips, 2013).

This evolving knowledge base is crucial for urban design decisions, particularly regarding the context and characteristics of urban spaces. (Nasar, 2011). architects and urban planners can craft environments that not only meet functional and aesthetic criteria but also positively influence the inhabitants' psychological well-being and social interactions. By integrating the principles of environmental psychology into their designs, (Weir, 2013). This synergy between environmental psychology and design has led to the development of spaces that are more accommodated to human needs and preferences, contributing to a higher quality of life for those who use them.

CHAPTER THREE

LITERATURE REVIEW

3. Overview

This chapter provides a comprehensive literature review of the evolution of the human-centered design approach in architecture, urban planning, and environmental psychology in part one. The second part of the chapter is an in-depth review of similar studies, the gap in the research, and identifying research variables.

3.1. Evolution of the human-centered design approach

The Human-centered approach promotes the design of any space with humans in mind (Yang et al., 2016). Before the development of environmental psychology, architects and urban planners relied on normative, often elusive concepts like "beautiful city " or "radiant city" to describe ideal urban environments (Lang, 1987). The more we understand human responses to the built environment, the better we can design toward these responses. Through a retrospective view of architectural development and urban theory, research on human-built environment interaction has become further influential since the decline of Modernism in the 1960s.

At that time, environmental and behavioral studies were concerned with the mutual interactions between people and the built environment and used traditional research techniques to obtain research evidence, such as surveys and observations (Lang, 1987, Rapoport, 1977). Following World War II, the modernist approach to urban planning, design, and Architecture brought order, uniformity, and segregation into urban settings.

This approach favored car-centric infrastructure more than pedestrian-friendly spaces and destroyed the city's social fabric. Modernist planners aimed for a futuristic aesthetic and efficiency but were criticized for creating sterile and disconnected urban environments (Jacob, 1961). Trauma from World War I influenced architects and planners, leading to the bare and emotionally detached design of modernism (Hollander and Sussman, 2020). Jane Jacob's work changed the paradigm of modern urban thinkers; as a result, architects and urban planners were able to construct urban spaces.

These spaces positively affect psychological well-being and social interactions through the integration of environmental psychology principles in the design process as shown in Figure 13, representing the timeline of human-centered concept evolution.

Figure 13 Evolution of Human-centered Design concept in architecture and urban planning, generated by Researcher from literature

3.1.1. Ancient Attempts in Human-Centered Design

In ancient times, Sthapatya Veda and Feng Shui were architectural systems from India and China, respectively, that have contributed to human-centric design by emphasizing harmony and well-being through architectural principles aligned with natural influences and cosmic energy.

Feng Shui created a balance of yin-yang of the five elements in the natural world. These systems reflect the deep connection between human life, architecture, and the environment (Sanskriti, 2023).

3.1.2. 1960s Advocacy for Human-Centered Urban Planning

Jane Jacobs in her 1961 book “*The Death and Life of Great American Cities*” opposed the idea of modernist planning. She advocated for a human-centric approach through direct observation and qualitative analysis. through a mixed-use approach to enhance social interactions, safety, control, sense of belonging, and place. Which ultimately prioritizes the needs and experiences of city dwellers (Jacob, 1961).

During the 1960s, there was a substantial witness of Environmental Psychology's maturation, particularly within urban studies. In Kevin Lynch's seminal work, "The Image

of the City," individuals created urban environments using cognitive maps to understand Imageability and navigation in urban spaces. His research significantly influenced the development of urban planning strategies that prioritize user experience and well-being, emphasizing elements like paths, edges, districts, nodes, and landmarks to enhance the sense of place (Lynch, 1964). Gordon Cullen's "The Concise Townscape" (1961) focused on how urban spaces can be designed to create engaging and emotionally experienced places for people.

Cullen introduced the concept of 'serial vision,' which refers to the experience of moving through a space and seeing a sequence of views. He argued that good urban spaces should be visually diverse, human-scaled, harmonious, reflect identity, and offer a sense of enclosure (Cullen, 1961).

3.1.3. Presenting Environmental Psychology of 1970 – 2000

Environmental psychology was established by Proshansky, Ittelson, and Rivlin as an interdisciplinary in their foundational work "Environmental Psychology: Man, and His Physical Setting" (1970). This discipline explored the complex interactions between humans and their physical environments, both natural and built. To understand how these environments influence human behavior, emotions, thoughts, and overall well-being. Environmental psychology was integrated into the planning and design of urban spaces. through considering physical, sociocultural, historical, and psychological dimensions of human-environment interactions. creating environments that support human well-being (Proshansky et al., 1970).

Later, Amos Rapoport in his book "*Human Aspects of Urban Form*" (1977), criticizes standardized modernist urban planning. He considered cultural background and the specific needs of communities. It was a human-centric approach that enriched the living experience and well-being of urban dwellers. Rapoport promoted a stronger sense of place in design by integrating human scale to foster identity, sensory experience, and adaptability.

His methodology integrates cross-cultural studies and environmental-behavior research for more inclusive and responsive urban spaces that value the lived experience and respect the complexity of human-environment interactions (Rapoport, 1977).

In the seminal work of William H. Whyte's "*The Street Life Project*" (1971) and "*The Social Life of Small Urban Spaces*" (1980), a bottom-up approach was advocated for

designing public spaces. To understand how people use and prefer to use urban spaces, that are easy to use, comfortable, and conducive to social interactions. Direct observation and the use of time-lapse photography methods were used to gather data on the social and spatial behavior of people in public spaces. His research aimed to identify why certain spaces are more attractive and functional than others, promoting the creation of livable communities (Whyte, 1980).

After William Whyte's approach, a vocal critic of modern urban planning was raised by Christopher Alexander (1977-1979) through participatory design approaches, fundamentally opposing the traditional top-down methodologies of modern urban planning; to respond to the daily needs of individuals.

In other publications by Alexander Christopher "*A Pattern Language*" (1977) and "*The Timeless Way of Building*" (1979), The value of involving residents in the design process, declaring that people inherently understand the needs of their urban environments better than planners or politicians. Alexander aimed to enrich human experiences by creating inclusive and responsive urban spaces. A profound impact was found across various fields through his methodology of observation and engagement with community members, including architecture, urban design, and sociology, to advocate for a user-driven, bottom-up approach to design (Alexander, 1977, Alexander, 1979).

Douglas Porteous, in "*Environment & Behavior: Planning and Everyday Urban Life*" (1977), integrates principles from Environmental Psychology, Behavioral Geography, and Urban Sociology, tackling the critical interaction between human behavior and urban environments in the context of planning practices. He emphasizes the importance of incorporating behavioral insights into urban planning and design to consider the everyday experiences of city dwellers. Porteous suggested that effective urban planning requires a deep understanding of human behavior (Porteous, 1977).

A Manual for Designers in 1985 was written by Ian Bentley, Alan Alcock, Paul Murrain, Sue McGlynn, and Graham Smith. They published a book named "Responsive Environments: Responsive Environments: A Manual for Designers" which presents a framework for creating urban spaces that prioritize human interaction, accessibility, and adaptability. The book introduces seven key principles including permeability, variety, legibility, robustness, visual appropriateness, richness, and personalization which guide the design of more responsive and engaging environments. Challenging the rigidity of

modernist planning, it emphasizes the direct impact of the built environment on social behavior and well-being. Its insights continue to shape contemporary urban design, advocating for spaces that enhance user experience and foster a stronger sense of place (Bentley et al., 1985).

Furthermore, Jan Gehl further advanced the discourse on urban environments with a profound emphasis on human-centric urban planning. In his pivotal works, notably "Life Between Buildings" (1987) Jan Gehl's advocacy for pedestrian-friendly, livable cities carried forward the baton, emphasizing the critical role of daily human activities in shaping urban spaces. Their contributions underlined the necessity for urban environments to evolve from mere places of transit to ones of interaction and human connection (Gehl, 1987).

Furthermore, another publication by Jan Gehl "*Public Spaces, Public Life*" (1996) emphasized a human-centric approach to urban design and planning, he advocated for cities that prioritize people over cars and more human scale than large-scale infrastructure. Gehl argues that well-designed public spaces enhance social interactions, walkability, and overall urban livability. His research, based on observational studies in Copenhagen, highlights how pedestrian-friendly environments contribute to vibrant urban life (Gehl and Gemzøe, 1996).

3.1.4. Period of 2000s the integration of Neuroscience

Jan Gehl in his pivotal works "*Life Between Buildings*," further developed his publications "*Cities for People*" (2010), and "*How to Study Public Life*" (2013) advocated for human-centric urban planning. Gehl prioritized human scale, sustainability, and social interaction in designing cities. He suggested urban spaces that are compact, safe, and vibrant, through design solutions that foster pleasant and functional public realms. Gehl's approach influenced interdisciplinary studies and practical methods were used to transform urban environments into settings that encourage public life and well-being (Gehl, 2010) (Gehl and Svarre, 2013).

In response, John Zeisel's work, particularly through the lens of the Environment /Behavior /Neuroscience (E/B/N) paradigm as outlined in "Inquiry by Design: Environment /Behavior/Neuroscience in Architecture, Interiors, Landscape, and Planning" (2006), integrated empirical research into design practices. His approach emphasized the critical importance of understanding the relationship between design

elements such as spatial layout, lighting, materials, color, nature integration, acoustics, human aspects, accessibility, and human experiences within built environments.

Zeisel advocated for evidence-based design decisions that foster physical and psychological well-being in architectural, landscape, and urban planning by drawing on insights from social sciences and neuroscience. His empirical research offers a comprehensive framework for creating healthier, more responsive, and human-centric environments. He encouraged interdisciplinary collaboration to improve the field of environmental design toward more sustainable and humane urban living spaces.

By using various methods such as physical tracking to understand how people navigate in public spaces, and behavioral observation to understand how children use playgrounds. He used interviews to recognize the needs of people with Alzheimer's disease in their living environments. Lastly, questionnaires were employed to survey cab drivers and street retailers about their preferred locations (Zeisel, 2006).

Similarly, Alain de Botton's "The Architecture of Happiness" investigated the psychological impact of architectural design on well-being; describing how physical surroundings influence our happiness. De Botton argued that the quality of the built environment affects our emotional state. His design philosophy acknowledged the deep connection between architecture and human happiness. The necessity of a people-centered approach in planning and design was advocated through thoughtful architectural elements like Natural Light, Materials, Spatial Harmony, Proportion, and Connection to Nature.

All that is to enhance human well-being and foster a deeper understanding of the human relationship with the built environment, where the quality of our environment plays a significant role in our happiness and misery (De Botton, 2008). Environmental psychology integrates social science methods to understand human experiences in real-world physical environments, emphasizing large-scale, multi-disciplinary perspectives for urban design decisions (Nasar, 2011). This synergy between environmental psychology and design has led to the development of spaces that are more accommodated to human needs and preferences, contributing to a higher quality of life for those who use them (Weir, 2013).

In 2014, Environmental Psychology and Neuroscience provided evidence-based criteria for designing human-friendly cities by examining people's experiences and behaviors in urban spaces. The human experience of physical space is a complex phenomenon that begins with perceiving the environment's sensory features. Based on this multisensory experience, cultural and personal factors, individuals recreate their understanding and

give value to the environment. Specifically, the human experience in an environment can be affected by different temporary and permanent conditions of the perceivers and of the environment itself (Piga and Morello, 2015).

3.1.5. The 21st-Century Paradigm Shift in Architecture and Planning

In recent years, advancements in neuroscientific methods have made it possible to study the influence of different built environments on human perception and affective states. The field of neuroarchitecture studies the effects of the built environment on its inhabitants by using neuroscientific tools. "Urban Experience and Design" published in 2020, highlighted the importance of the unconscious mind's processes in shaping human interaction within urban environments.

They advocate for integrating insights from neuroscience and cognitive science into urban planning to enhance the relevance and effectiveness of public spaces. Key concepts included the importance of biophilic design for physical and mental health, learning from architectural history to create spaces that foster a sense of belonging and well-being, and designing with an understanding of human unconscious responses. The book argued for a paradigm shift toward planning and architecture that prioritizes human psychological and emotional needs, using biometric tools like EEG for a more intuitive and engaging urban experience (Hollander and Sussman, 2020).

In "Cognitive Architecture" (2021), Ann Sussman and Justin B. Hollander advocated for creating more effective, human-centric spaces. Human evolutionary psychology and cognitive responses were integrated into architectural and urban design. Human interactions with the built environment can be achieved through design elements such as edges, patterns, symmetry, narratives, and biophilia. These preferences are linked to the evolutionary psychology of humans, they influence safety, aesthetic comfort, cognitive engagement, and well-being (Sussman and Hollander, 2021). The researcher used biometric tools like eye tracking, facial expression analysis, EEG, and galvanic skin response sensors to document unconscious reactions to the design of the built environment.

Table 1 brief description of the evolution of the human-centred design approach, key contributions, and concepts

Decade	Theorist(s)	Key Contribution	Main Ideas and Year of Contribution
1960s	Jane Jacobs	Human-centric urban planning	Advocated for mixed-use development, enhancing social interactions and sense of place. (1961)
1960s	Kevin Lynch	Cognitive mapping in urban environments	Introduced the concept of "Imageability" and the importance of paths, edges, districts, nodes, and landmarks. (1964)
1960s	Gordon Cullen	Visual and emotional engagement in urban design	Introduced "serial vision" and principles for engaging in public space design, such as visual diversity and identity. (1961)
1970s	Proshansky, & Rivlin	Foundational work in Environmental Psychology	Emphasized the impact of environments on behavior and well-being. (1970)
1970s	Amos Rapoport	Human aspects of urban form	Criticized standardized planning, promoting cultural responsiveness and mixed-use developments. (1977)
1970s	William H. Whyte	The social life of urban spaces	Utilized direct observation and time-lapse photography to understand public space use. (1971, 1980)
1970s	Christopher Alexander	Participatory design and pattern language	Emphasized community involvement in design, focusing on practical, lived solutions. (1977, 1979)
1970s	J. Douglas Porteous	Environmental Behavior and Urban Planning	Advocating for a design adapted to human behavior. (1977)
1980s	Ian Bentley, Alan Alcock, Paul Murrain, Sue McGlynn, Graham Smith	Responsive urban environments	Introduced seven key design principles: permeability, variety, legibility, robustness, visual appropriateness, richness, and personalization to create adaptable, engaging urban spaces. (1985)
1980s-2010s	Jan Gehl	Human-centric urban planning and public spaces	Prioritized human scale, sustainability, and social interaction in urban design.
2000s	John Zeisel	Environment /Behavior /Neuroscience E/B/N paradigm	Integrated empirical research into design, emphasizing the impact of design elements on human experiences. (2006)
2000s	Alain de Botton	The psychological impact of the built environment	Explored how architecture influences happiness and well-being. (2008)

2020s	Hollander & Sussman	Biophilic design and neuroscience in urban planning	Advocated designs that enhance psychological and emotional needs, using biometric tools. (2020)
2021s	Sussman & Hollander	Unconscious - Cognitive responses in architecture	Focused on how evolutionary psychology influences our interaction with built environments. (2021)

3.2. Related studies

The section reviews recent studies and research exploring the interaction between human and environmental criteria. The research was selected based on its relevance to the research aims, focusing on the impact of built environment elements on human emotions and perceptual responses. The following studies provide a deeper understanding of how physical elements impact human well-being by examining different methodological approaches and recent tools.

3.2.1. Mapping Feeling: An Approach to the Study of Emotional Response to the Built Environment and Landscape (Weinreb and Rofè, 2013)

In the realm of environmental psychology, the study offers a novel perspective on how urban design influences emotional well-being. It utilized the method of 'feeling maps', this research provides a better understanding of the emotional responses provoked by the built environment in Mitzpe Ramon, Israel.

The study captures the contrast of positive and negative feelings across various urban spaces in the city, identifying the “feeling map” generated by the researcher, which included the affective areas in the urban environment that consistently evoke strong emotional responses from the residents, whether positive or negative.

In conclusion, Spaces that combined greenery, pathways, and views of the natural landscape with architectural elements elicited strong positive feelings. This underscores the significance of incorporating nature and thoughtful design in urban spaces to enhance emotional well-being.

3.2.2. Tracking Emotions in Urban Space: Two Experiments in Vienna and Siena (Capineri et al., 2018)

In this study attributed to the Vienna University of Technology, researchers aimed to understand the impact of urban environments on people's emotional well-being using the

EmoMap app for data collection. participants provided self-reported emotional feedback while navigating different areas, with a particular focus on how traffic density and the presence of vegetation influenced their comfort levels.

The research used a 7-point Likert scale and a set of emotional adjectives. The study measured comfort, contextual factors such as the presence of people, and familiarity with the location. Findings revealed that greener spaces were associated with higher comfort levels, whereas areas with heavy traffic were linked to discomfort.

3.2.3. Field analysis of psychological effects of urban design: A case study in Vancouver (Negami et al., 2018)

This research investigates the psychological effects of urban design elements within urban settings. urban design elements selected as independent variables were “Colorful walkways, community gardens, formal green spaces, and intersection or nodes design” and the main psychological factors such as “Social interaction, mental well-being, and a sense of community engagement”. Psychological responses were evaluated, ranging from feelings of control to environmental perception and overall attraction to space. The study employed a smartphone application to distribute a comprehensive questionnaire. Participants provided feedback on various aspects of urban spaces they visited, offering insights into their levels of arousal, perceived pleasantness, interest, attraction, and willingness to engage within these environments.

Findings revealed a clear link between urban design elements incorporating greenery and community-focused initiatives and elevated happiness levels, improved moods, and well-being.

3.2.4. Seeing the City: using eye-tracking Technology to explore cognitive responses to the Built Environment (Hollander et al., 2018)

The study aimed to explore cognitive responses to the built environment through the lens of eye-tracking technology. The research hypothesized that urban environments designed with certain characteristics could influence unconscious eye movements and evoke positive cognitive responses.

Independent Variables used were Urban design characteristics based on Cognitive Architecture principles (edges, facades/patterns, shapes, narrative/historical, natural elements). Dependent Variables were Eye movements (fixations, saccades, blink rate, scan path lengths), and emotional reactions (likelihood to spend time in the environment,

relaxation levels). The study utilized controlled indoor labs and real-world environments to test these principles. Participants viewed images representing different urban environments while their eye movements were recorded, Subsequent surveys assessed their emotional reactions to these images. The qualitative assessment of eye movement activity suggested a cognitive preference of users. Survey responses indicated that environments demonstrating Cognitive Architecture principles were associated with more positive reactions in terms of spending time and feeling relaxed.

3.2.5. Affective experiences of built environments and promotion of urban walking (Bornioli et al., 2019)

The study aims to understand how the affective experiences of built environments influence people's intentions to walk in urban settings. It focused on design elements like aesthetic appeal, traffic presence, city busyness, and pedestrian infrastructure within various urban environments, ranging from historic pedestrianized areas to modern developments and urban greens. The researchers employed an experimental design involving virtual exposure to five different environments, followed by evaluations of affective experiences and walking intentions. Participants gave their insights through photo-elicited interviews.

The study discovered that environmental design elements like aesthetic structures, engaging and attractive surroundings, and well-designed pedestrian infrastructure were key positive factors that encouraged walking behavior in urban settings.

3.2.6. Aesthetical cognitive perceptions of urban street form (D'Acci, 2019)

In a study conducted by Luca D'Acci, the primary aim was to delve into pedestrian preferences for street forms within urban settings, with a particular focus on the aesthetic appeal of straight versus curvy paths. Using a questionnaire, D'Acci could select street form as the main variable of interest. Through quantitative analysis of participants' responses, the study uncovered a preference for curvy paths, which participants found to be not only more aesthetically pleasing but also perceived as shorter.

3.2.7. Erbil City Built Heritage and Wellbeing: An Assessment of Local Perceptions Using the Semantic Differential Scale (Sektani et al., 2021)

As one of the first studies of its kind in the local context, perceptions of built heritage and its effects on well-being were assessed together by (Sektani et al., 2021) aiming to explore local perceptions of built heritage in Erbil City.

The methodology employed involved a questionnaire survey with 414 participants, utilizing the Semantic Differential Scale to measure reactions to images of both high-quality heritage buildings and contrasting modern structures within Erbil's Citadel buffer zone. The research accurately categorized variables into qualitative attributes (visual stimuli), heritage-value attributes (perception of heritage value), and affective-evaluative attributes (emotional responses and preferences), with participants' responses collected on a 5-point scale.

The findings revealed stark differences in perceptions between architects and non-architects, showing that architects generally attribute more positive values to heritage buildings, whereas non-architects exhibited a preference for modern over heritage buildings. In conclusion, the study suggests that implementing education programs to raise local awareness about the value of built heritage are crucial step towards enhancing perceptions. Additionally, it recommends developing design regulations that balance heritage features with contemporary development, ensuring the integrity of heritage buildings.

3.2.8. Use of electroencephalography (EEG) for comparing study of the external space perception of traditional and modern commercial districts (Sun et al., 2021)

The study aimed to evaluate the differences in physiological and psychological perceptions between traditional and modern commercial districts, highlighting the importance of preservation, regeneration, and sustainably developing traditional commercial districts. The electroencephalography EEG was a tool for external space evaluation and interpreting EEG data with subjective perception.

This research utilized the electroencephalography (EEG) test and the Semantic Differential (SD) method to assess human perceptions of traditional and modern commercial districts objectively both conscious and unconscious responses. EEG Alpha Wave was used to measure the physiological response (comfort and relaxation levels) of participants to traditional versus modern commercial districts. Results Captured subjective evaluations of traditional versus modern districts in terms of comfort, relaxation, cultural atmosphere, and spatial openness/closedness.

EEG results indicated that the alpha wave meant value of traditional samples was greater than that of modern samples across all electrodes, suggesting a significant difference in physiological response favoring traditional districts. SD results showed that traditional

districts were perceived as more comfortable, relaxing, and culturally rich compared to modern districts. The study also found significant correlations between alpha wave values and certain spatial and visual elements, such as the sense of open and closed space, the amount of visible sky, and the simplicity of colors in traditional districts.

3.2.9. Embodied response to the public realm: applying embodied cognition to people's experience of public space (Eldridge, 2022)

This research aims to understand how urban design affects human cognition and emotional responses by integrating embodied cognition theory with electroencephalography (EEG) technology. Employing a mixed-methods approach, this research engaged 20 participants in experiencing two public plazas in Sydney, Australia, assessing their conscious and unconscious reactions to key urban design elements through surveys, walking interviews, and EEG measurements. The study's variables included positive attraction, stimulation, stress, and relaxation. Findings revealed that EEG data highlighting significant stress and stimulation that surveys and interviews alone did not fully capture. However, discrepancies between expected and actual EEG responses for positive attraction and relaxation pointed to the complex nature of human-environment interactions.

These results suggest future research should broaden the scope of environments studied and refine the understanding of unconscious responses to design elements, aiming to guide the creation of more cognitive and emotionally supportive urban spaces.

3.2.10. Impact of Connection with Nature on Users' Satisfaction in Architecture Design Studios (Khayat and Basheer, 2023)

The study explores the influence of biophilic design, integrating natural elements into built environments on the satisfaction levels of users, specifically architecture students in design studios. The study delves into both visual and non-visual connections with nature within the context of architectural education spaces across several universities in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq (KRI). Through a comprehensive survey involving 355 participants from seven different universities, the research seeks to understand how the inclusion of nature in interior spaces affects the well-being and academic satisfaction of students. The key findings of the research highlight a general dissatisfaction among students regarding both visual and non-visual connections with nature in their design studio environments.

The study categorizes biophilic design patterns into two main types for analysis: visual connections with nature (such as views of the outdoors, natural light, and incorporation of natural materials and motifs) and non-visual connections (involving auditory, olfactory, and haptic experiences of nature). The results indicate that most of the surveyed design studios lack effective integration of these biophilic elements, leading to a conclusion that the presence of nature or natural elements in educational settings is directly linked to higher levels of student satisfaction.

Table 2 Related studies and recent research

No	Author	Purpose	Methods	Research variables	Results
1	(Weinreb and Rofé, 2013)	Emotional data gathering	feeling map through self-report	Streets, public spaces, green buildings	Physical attributes strongly influence emotions, both positively and negatively.
2	(Capineri et al., 2018)	the levels of comfort or discomfort in urban spaces	EmoMap application to collect affective responses	Traffic congestion and Natural areas	Green areas receive the most positive ratings, and heavily trafficked areas receive negative ratings
3	(Negami et al., 2018)	urban design elements impact psychological well-being.	Questionnaire distributed via smartphone app	crosswalks, green space green, and standard, laneways	Greenery and community-centric initiatives were associated with higher happiness and attraction among participants.
4	(Hollander et al., 2018)	Urban environments influence cognitive responses	emotional reactions of elements, through eye movement	edges, shapes, patterns, narrative, biophilia	Well-defined edges, appealing facades and patterns, natural elements, and narrative spaces made users feel relaxed
5	(Bormioli et al., 2019)	affective experiences and people's intentions to walk in urban areas	virtual exposure to environment, and self-report affective experiences	aesthetic appeal, traffic presence, city busyness, and pedestrian infrastructure	Key factors encouraging walking included pleasant aesthetics, engaging surroundings, and well-designed pedestrian infrastructure.

6	(D'Acci, 2019)	investigate pedestrian preferences between straight and curvy urban street paths	Self-reporting questionnaire	street form (straight vs. curvy) and pedestrians' perception of aesthetic and path length.	The research found a significant preference for curvy paths, which were perceived as aesthetically more pleasing and shorter.
7	(Sektani et al., 2021)	perceptions of built heritage in Erbil and its Impact on Community Wellbeing	Semantic Differential Scale	high-quality heritage buildings and contrasting modern buildings	Significant differences were found between the perceptions of architects and non-architects, with architects attributing more positive values to heritage buildings compared to non-architects.
8	(Sun et al., 2021)	Comparison of traditional and modern districts' brain activity	EEG for brain activity Semantic Differential for perception.	Heritage, and Modern built environment	EEG and SD results showed that traditional districts were perceived as more comfortable, relaxing, and culturally rich.
9	(Eldridge, 2022)	Urban design influences human cognitive and emotional responses,	walking interviews with (EEG) to measure both conscious and unconscious responses	Orderly design and pattern. Openness and Natural and fabricated elements. Upkeep spaces. Liveliness and people.	EEG data emphasized significant stress and stimulation that surveys and interviews alone did not fully capture. Those negative effects were a response to the counterpart of the research variables.
10	(Khayat and Basheer, 2023)	investigate the effect of biophilic design patterns on users' satisfaction and well-being	Quantitative approach with a survey questionnaire	Visual and non-visual connections with nature in architecture design studios	General dissatisfaction among architecture students with the level of nature integration in their studios.

The table (3) below categorizes key study variables that have occurred in recent relevant studies and research. These variables were examined across ten studies, identified by their

author and publication year, spanning from 2013 to 2023. The table has been systematically arranged to compare the frequency of these terms, to gather research insights, and to find the potential gaps within the research field.

Table 3 variables from related studies and research

Main Variables	Sub-variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Scoring
		(Negami et al., 2018)	(Weinreb and Rofe, 2013)	(Capineri et al., 2018)	(Bornioli et al., 2019)	(Hollander et al., 2018)	(D'Acci, 2019)	(Sektani et al., 2021)	(Khayat and Basheer, 2023)	(Sun et al., 2021)	(Eldridge, 2022)	
Built Environments	Historical				•	•		•		•		4
	Modern				•			•		•		3
design principles	Openness		•		•					•	•	4
	Harmony/ balance		•		•	•						3
	Symmetry					•						1
	curves					•						1
Narrative Elements	Aesthetic Structures		•		•	•					•	4
	Public Art	•			•							2
Physical features	pavements	•			•		•				•	4
	Shading				•	•						2
	Pedestrian access	•		•			•					3
	Edges					•						1
	Building Scale					•				•		2
Biophilia	Greenery	•	•	•	•	•			•		•	7
	Materials/ patterns	•				•	•		•		•	6
	Water features								•		•	2

3.3. Identifying the research gap

In the process of selecting research variables for the study, there was a focus on identifying the key elements addressing the gap highlighted in literature and similar research. A considerable amount of research has explored the relationship between the psychological state of mind and the built environment and planning. The identified gaps were as follows:

- Lack of studies combining multiple variables.
- Limited research on cultural diversity's influence on human-environment interaction, especially in Kurdistan.
- To further investigate why regional contexts may shape perceptual responses differently from Western settings (Sektani et al., 2021).
- Insufficient understanding of the synergistic effects of combined built environment elements.
- Need for research on how the research variables influence the human state of mind by using no limitation when collecting perceptual responses, in order to understand the factors influencing local perception.
- Absence of studies on the historic, narrative, and biophilic urban environment of Duhok in urban design and planning.

3.4. Research variables

This section introduces the main research variables of the research, examining the impact of important elements in urban built environments that influence the Human state of mind. Further, independent variables like Historic, natural, and narrative-built environments are the factors to be studied for their impact on the dependent variable.

The human state of mind, which indicates the perceptual and emotional experience of the residents, reflects the outcome or impact on human mental well-being. This section aims to discuss and introduce the research variables that will be studied in the Context of Duhok City and their role in urban space design and built environment design.

3.4.1. Independent Variables

The independent Variables of the research are as follows:

3.4.1.1. Historic urban elements

Historic urban environments play a crucial role in preserving cultural identity, fostering community pride, and contributing to the aesthetic and historical value of cities. Historic buildings and sites serve as tangible links to the past, offering insights into the ancient, architectural, and cultural narratives of urban development.

According to (Smith, 2006) The historic urban environment is not only about preserving physical structures but also about maintaining the cultural dynamics and memories associated with these sites. This includes the architectural and historical significance that adds to the unique character of urban environments. Moreover, heritage conservation can enhance tourism, provide educational opportunities, and support sustainable urban development by integrating historical elements into modern city planning (Logan, 2012). According to (Hollander and Sussman, 2020) Spaces with Historical elements can evoke personal or collective memories and foster a deeper emotional connection enhancing place identity, meaning, and engagement to a place.

Gehl (2010) emphasizes the importance of scale, proportion, and composition in creating visually pleasing urban spaces which are mostly found in Historic structures as mentioned earlier. Color further contributes to this perception; as Nasar (1998) notes, color can affect mood and the perceived attractiveness of an environment. The preservation of heritage sites helps to create a sense of place and continuity, fostering a deeper connection between residents and their environment (Tunbridge, 2000).

3.4.1.2. Narrativity in Urban Spaces Design

Narrativity is defined as the capacity to evoke stories through elements that do not tell a story themselves, such as buildings, maps, or urban forms. These elements can suggest or bring to mind particular stories by their design, context, or symbolism (Ameel et al., 2023).

This concept emphasizes the connection between urban development and an area's existing history or community heritage. Planning with narrativity aims to create place identities and evoke a sense of continuity by incorporating historical elements, local

stories, and cultural symbols into the urban landscape. Narratives for Planning involve drawing on existing local stories, oral histories, and cultural representations to inform and guide the planning process (Ameel et al., 2023). By using narratives, planners can make urban spaces more meaningful and engaging for the community, fostering a deeper connection between people and their environment. This approach also helps in making planning documents more persuasive and relatable by sitting in developing within a broader historical and cultural context .

This approach ensures coherence in design, adds curiosity, attracts visitors, and strengthens community identity. “Narrativity” Influences the perception and value of urban spaces. Stories enrich places with personality, identity, and emotional resonance, transforming ordinary locations into meaningful places for communities and individuals. essentially give a place a kind of personality, individuality, and identity (Timmermans et al., 2013). Understanding narrative sequencing in architecture or urban planning highlights how people seek connections and meaning in their surroundings, from buildings to urban designs. This perspective emphasizes the importance of creating environments that resonate with individuals' innate desire to form attachments and find significance, rather than contributing to a sense of placelessness or disconnection. This approach can fundamentally inform and enrich architectural and urban planning projects, making them more engaging and meaningful for the community (Sussman and Hollander, 2021). Narrative urban environments are crafted through the integration of both tangible and intangible elements as shown in Figure 14, which collectively narrate the story of a place. These elements are fundamental in creating a cohesive and immersive urban experience (Follesa et al., 2021).

Figure 14 Cultural Identity of the Cities—The Use of Narratives. Source: (Follesa et al., 2021)

3.4.1.3. Biophilic/ Natural Elements

Biophilic design represents an approach that integrates our inherent connection to the natural environment into modern architecture and urban planning. This concept is rooted in the recognition that human evolution occurred within the natural world, which fundamentally shaped our physiological and psychological makeup.

Edward O. Wilson, in his seminal 1984 work, advocated for a deeper understanding and remembrance of our bond with nature. This perspective forms the foundation of biophilic design, which strives to acknowledge and nurture our connections to the natural world for our health, productivity, and overall well-being (Wilson, 1986).

Stephen Kellert, along with Judith Heerwagen and Martin Mador in their 2008 book "Biophilic Design: The Theory, Science, and Practice of Bringing Buildings to Life," critiques modern building practices that often create a sense of 'placelessness,' characterized by monotonous and artificial environments. Such designs, he claims, contribute to sensory deprivation and a general dulling of human senses, underscoring a visual deterioration in our urban landscapes (Kellert et al., 2011).

The biophilic design challenges the prevailing architectural norms by promoting spaces that reconnect us to the natural settings, which span from the African savannas to the grasslands of Europe and Asia. These environments, marked by their complex natural landscapes, were integral to the development of human cognitive and physical traits (Kellert, 2012).

Biophilic design, which integrates natural elements like "Water features, natural materials, nature-inspired motifs, textures, natural shapes, and forms, natural light, and air" into urban environments, is increasingly recognized for its profound impact on human well-being. Naturally inspired Patterns, and motifs, face bias facades Fractal patterns, ornamentation visual interest, and engagement, contribute to a sense of beauty linking them to human comfort and aesthetic preference (Ruggles and Boak, 2020, Hollander et al., 2018, Hollander and Sussman, 2020).

Recent scholarly work continues to underscore the importance of this connection, Research reveals that maintaining a link to these natural settings is essential for nurturing our mental, physical, and spiritual health. In essence, biophilic design is not merely an aesthetic choice but a necessity for enhancing human well-being in the built environment.

Experiencing nature and its visual complexity, even for a few minutes, even represented in a painting or photography, reduces stress and has other benefits (Ulrich, 2002).

Biophilic design not only emphasizes the visual integration of nature into the built environment but also delves into the inherent human responses to various forms of physical spaces (Wilson, 1986). This concept is based on the idea that humans have an innate affinity with nature, which is essential for their physical and mental health. By incorporating natural elements into the urban fabric, biophilic design fosters connectivity between people and nature, improving the quality of life in cities.

3.4.2. Dependent variable: human state of mind

The "human state of mind" refers to the psychological condition of a person at a given time, influenced by both internal and external factors. It encompasses a range of mental states, including emotions, thoughts, perceptions, and consciousness. Understanding the human state of mind is crucial in various fields, such as psychology, psychiatry, neuroscience, and urban planning, as it affects behavior, well-being, and interactions with the environment.

3.4.2.1. Emotional State

Emotions such as happiness, sadness, anxiety, and calmness play a significant role in the human state of mind. They are influenced by personal experiences, environmental factors, and physiological conditions (Izard, 2009).

3.4.2.2. Perception

These include thoughts, beliefs, and perceptions that shape how individuals interpret and respond to their surroundings. Cognitive processes are fundamental in understanding how people make decisions and solve problems (Beck, 2019).

3.5. Summary

The chapter comprehends the evolution of human-centered design and the advocacy for a more human-centered approach to city planning. It further investigated the most recent studies and research that better the understanding of this relationship between humans and their living environment. Overall, the chapter sets the foundation for identifying the role of urban environments in enhancing human emotional well-being and experiences. Research gaps and variables were highlighted in the final section of the chapter and

briefly explained the study aims. In conclusion, the conceptual framework of the study was generated as shown in figure 15.

Figure 15 Conceptual Research Framework, Source: Developed by Researcher

CHAPTER FOUR RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4. Overview

This chapter explains the research methodology used in this study to investigate the perceptual experience and emotional responses of Duhok City's inhabitants. The section starts with explaining the study area and the selection criteria, main features, and potentialities for the study objectives. Later, the sample selection and size, data collection, and data analysis methods are explained in this chapter.

Study Area Duhok City: Geography and Demographic Context

Duhok City is located in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, North of Erbil. It serves as a crucial connection point between Iraq, the Kurdistan region, Syria, and Turkey as Figure 16. The city is situated at coordinates (37°3'N 43°9'E / 37.05°N 43.15°E) in the northern equinoctial area. The city lies in a wide valley flanked by two opposing mountain ranges, Bekhair to the north and northeast, and Zaiwa to the southeast. This topographical setting creates a unique and scenic urban landscape dominated by mountains.

Figure 16 Administrative map of Iraq (Mapssite, 2009)

sits at an elevation of 430-450 meters above sea level. Duhok's strategic location at the borders with Turkey, Syria, and northern Iraq enhances its importance in regional trade and economic activities. The population of Duhok city has experienced significant growth, particularly after 1998, due to the influx of internally displaced persons (IDPs) and Syrian refugees. The population increased by approximately 69% since 1998, reaching around 360,000 inhabitants by 2019 (Directorate of Statistics in Duhok Province, 2019). This rapid growth has led to congestion and overcrowding in the city.

4.1.1. History of the City

Duhok has historically held a strategic geographical position. It was a contested area between various ancient powers, including the Assyrians and Mitanni (Ghafour, 2021). Despite these conflicts, Duhok maintained its identity as a key commercial hub, located at the junction of Iraq, Turkey, and Syria, and serving as a gateway to Iraqi Kurdistan. The city was part of the Badinan Emirate from the 14th to the 18th century until 1842. Later, it joined the Mosul Brigade, and in 1969, the Duhok Governorate was established, previously part of the Nineveh Governorate. The city has numerous heritage sites reflecting its rich history, in recent decades, rural-urban migration and the return of refugees have significantly increased the population. The Anfal campaigns (1978-1989) displaced thousands and destroyed many villages, leading to unplanned urban expansion. Many immigrants settled in the city, particularly in the southern, western, and eastern parts. Following the 1991 uprising and the establishment of a No-Fly Zone, Iraqi Kurdistan has functioned as a de facto state under the Kurdistan Regional Government. Today, the region, and Duhok in particular, is known for its relative peace and stability.

4.1.2. Evolution of the City Center Area

Over the past 35 years, Duhok City has experienced significant expansion. The city's core was originally a compact area of approximately 2 km by 2 km. Today, Duhok has grown into a more extensive urban strip measuring about 15 km in length and 3 km in width. The historical heart of Duhok, some of which falls within the current boundaries of Duhok City Center, was located to the east of the Gelli River.

Figure 17 Duhok Cadastral Map 1923 - 1964 original copy Source: "Duhok Planning department"

This historic core included important areas such as the souq (market), the Jewish Quarter, and the northern part of the Shele neighborhood. Figure 17 illustrates that in the early 1920s, the urban structure of Duhok City included the Souq area, what is now known as the Jewish Quarter, and the Dasinya Quarter as shown in Figure 18. During this period, the city center was entirely located on the right bank of the river basin. This area was elevated and enclosed by agricultural land, indicating a strategic choice for settlement.

Duhok City found a major growth in 1975, the population was approximately 21,266. At that time, the city's expansion was limited to the historical quarters mentioned earlier, along with some discrete vernacular settlements on the opposite side of the Gelli River. Consequently, before 1970, nearly half of the City Center was uninhabited. By overlaying the base map obtained from the survey and aerial photographs, an analysis of the street patterns was conducted.

Figure 19 highlights the historical street patterns still preserved in certain areas, particularly in the Souq area and Sheile Quarter. The identification of these historical streets has informed the development of a Conservation Plan for the Jewish Quarter (Regeneration Area 08) and serves as a guiding principle for creating a Detailed Conservation Plan for the Traditional Souq in the future (directorate of planning) The further expansion of Duhok is depicted in Figure 18. The brown areas in the center represent the parts of the city that were developed by the early 1980s. The red and violet areas indicate developments that occurred after 1984. The boundary of Duhok City Center now encompasses most of these historic areas, classified as the "Center," along with the 1973 expansion.

Figure 18 Duhok Urban Development and Growth. Master plan of Duhok City Source (A.R.S.progetti, 2014)

Focusing on Duhok City Center, it encompasses multiple municipal districts, each contributing to the diverse and vibrant character of the area. Specifically, the city center's boundary includes parts of the Dasinya, Bazar, Brayati, Shaheedan, Gre Base, Nawroz, Nohadra, Mazi, and Shele districts as in Figure 19.

Figure 19 Duhok City Centre Boundary and Its Distribution Among Different Municipal Districts (A.R.S.progetti, 2014)

4.1.3. Characteristics of the City Center Zones

The City Center is divided into nine separate zones, each classified according to its current uses, morphological characteristics, and development objectives.

The zones are identified as follows: Zone A is the prevalent commercial zone encompassing Nohadra and South Newroz Quarters; Zone B is the prevalent commercial zone covering the Souq and Brayati Quarter; Zone C is the prevalent commercial central block within Nohadra Quarter; Zone D is the prevalent commercial zone in Shaheedan Quarter; Zone E is the prevalent commercial zone in Mazi Quarter; Zone F is the prevalent residential zone in Gree Base Quarter; Zone G is the prevalent historical neighborhood zone in the Jewish Quarter; Zone I represents green areas, and Zone H is the prevalent residential zone in Shaheedan Quarter.

Figure 20 Duhok City Center eight distinct zones source: (A.R.S.progetti, 2014)

The area of the study will encompass Zone I, and Zone G as depicted in Figure 20, in the city center of Duhok which includes the three environments relevant to the study. These zones have been identified due to their significant functions, activities, and landmarks as highlighted by the Department of Planning and Heritage.

4.2. Rationale selection of the case study Area

The selection of Zones I, and G, as the case study area is rooted in their prominence within the city center of Duhok. These zones are rich in important functions and activities, hosting several landmark buildings and historic sites that are crucial to the urban fabric of Duhok. The Department of Planning and Heritage has underscored the significance of these areas, making them ideal for studying the impact of urban design on human experiences. This research seeks to bridge this gap by studying the spatial experiences within the selected zones of Duhok, ultimately aiming to suggest a model that enhances the quality of these experiences through informed urban design practices. The case study area is relevant to the Research Goals as follows:

- To study Perceptual and Emotional Experience: the selected Zones offer a varied urban environment, which is critical for analyzing how different urban designs impact their users' perceptual and emotional experiences. By focusing on these areas, the research can capture a wide range of perceptions and emotional responses elicited by different types of urban environments.
- Human-Environment Interactions: The chosen areas provide a rich context for exploring the interplay between humans and their environment. The presence of

heritage sites, public squares, and diverse architectural styles enables a detailed examination of how these elements interact with human activities to create a more humanistic quality in Urban spaces.

4.2.1. Observation of Duhok City Center from Human City Approach

A human-centered city prioritizes its residents to meet the needs of all social groups and provides a pleasant, healthy environment with accessible green spaces and social public areas. However, modern cities have strayed from this idea, progressively ignoring the human aspect. With 50% of the world's population currently living in cities, this statistic is expected to escalate to 70% by 2050 (Unesco, 2016).

Urban planning in Duhok City has heavily focused on vehicle movement, neglecting the human dimension. Consequently, residents face a lack of pedestrian-friendly environments, dwindling green spaces, climate impact, pollution, inadequate housing and services, traffic congestion, unemployment, social inequality, societal tension, and insecurity, all in all negatively impacting well-being.

4.2.2. Street design and Transportation in the city center of Duhok

Many urban areas today face significant problems due to city planning strategies that favor cars over people, with Duhok being one such city. One of the most critical issues is the preference for other transportation modes over walking. This preference leads to numerous challenges, such as higher pollution levels, health and psychological issues, and the hazards associated with car accidents. Researchers have observed the pattern of street design, accessibility, vehicles, and pedestrian paths.

Most of the roads in Duhok city center were structured mainly for cars, not people. As cars became more popular worldwide, pedestrians had less space on sidewalks. This led to crowded sidewalks, which became a widespread issue, as shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Photo by the Researcher, showing the dominance of Cars over pedestrians.

The selected zones were as follows:

4.2.3. Nawroz Park: Natural Environment and Narrative Elements

The total area of the park is around 12418 m², It is located in the city center of Duhok City, as shown in Figure 22. The park is divided into two zones; the green area indicates Hi Park, which indicates the natural environment identified in the study. This area occupies 2161 m² of green coverage, it includes a total ornamental plants are 378 green elements (Hammo and Mohammed, 2023), water features, historical structures, and natural materials like stone as illustrated in Figure 22.

Figure 22 Satellite image for Nawroz Park in Duhok City Centre, source: Google map

Figure 23 Images representing Hi Park, taken for the natural environment of study, Source: Researcher.

The park is surrounded by four laneways one is the main street of Duhok Bazaar which is mostly vehicle-oriented, the others are less busy with cars. Three entrances, one on the main street two from the sides of the Nawroz Park area, and one gate from the old “Fine Art Institute building” but it is not functional yet. Nawroz Park is recognized as mostly pavement with less green and natural elements. Newroz Park is a blend of old buildings that reflect the historical and cultural narrative of the area, alongside modern architectural designs that represent the city's progress and future orientation.

Figure 24 Narrative elements found in Nawroz Park and surrounding areas, Source: taken by Researcher

Figure 24 depicts the "statues, public Art, amphitheater, Fire torch monument, and historical structures" that are among the narrative elements present in the study area. The first primary school in the city, known as "The First School," was constructed in the 1920s, according to the Heritage and Antiquities Department of Duhok, and is signified as a historical asset for the city. The school was Constructed with organic stone, it is intended to be preserved by the department as a historic asset. In addition to being an old building material, it also symbolizes "power," "wealth," and "belonging" in contemporary society (Shareef and Sani, 2021). Subsequently, the structure was transformed into the Institution of Fine Arts, while the sculptures in the park's surrounding streets depict student artwork that endured as narrative components.

The artwork in Figure 28 shows a traditional Kurdish woman, and the sun symbol stands for the revival of Kurdistan's historic civilization. In Kurdish culture, the fire torch is a representation of unity among the citizens and the Nawroz Festival, which marks the start of spring and the new year (Kurdistan24, 2024). In General, Nawroz Park highlights a vital space in Duhok City, it was selected for its diverse character, which represents a blend of different natural, historical, and narrative elements.

4.2.4. Jewish neighborhood: Historic urban environment

The Jewish neighborhood in Duhok city is a historically significant residential area developed by the Jewish community that resided earlier in the city. The neighborhood was built in the 16th to early 20th Century, it grew organically as the Jewish population resettled in Duhok city. The urban design is developed as the traditional Middle Eastern model of narrow and winding streets that were designed to provide natural ventilation and shading, which helps to mitigate the harsh summer climate as depicted in Figure 25.

Figure 25 The images represent the narrow and winding streets used in traditional structures. Source: taken by Researcher

The layout of these narrow winding streets can also facilitate social interaction within the community in Middle Eastern traditional architecture (Nooraddin, 1998). While the local Jewish efforts mainly developed the neighborhood, it was still influenced by the Kurdish urban design principles that could balance the religious needs and environmental and social needs of the time. The exodus of Jews from Iraq in the 1950s resulted in the decline of these neighborhoods; most of these buildings were either repurposed or abandoned (Duhok: Antiquities, 2024).

4.2.4.1. Architectural Features and Elements

The main features of these structures were thick walls as shown in Figure 29, and flat roofs unified in all buildings with harmonious scale and height to cope with the climate of the region (Duhok: Antiquities, 2024). The architectural features (volume and facade composition, decoration, materials, and similar building techniques) still reflect these

historic remnants. Gates of “monumental” or outstanding values, and structures in wood or metal as depicted in Figure 26.

Figure 26 The images represent the thickness of the walls found in the historic structures in the Jewish Neighbourhood, Source: Taken by Researcher

The original brickwork and stone structures are still in place, the façade was lime-washed in the traditional colors in one or two tones of the same color as depicted in Figure 27.

Figure 27 The Architectural elements in Jewish Neighbourhood Historic structures, Source: (A.R.S.progetti, 2014)

Parapets and railings in heritage and vernacular buildings are constructed with wrought iron or masonry Canopies as evidence of the existence of such elements in past times as depicted in Figures 28 and 29. The typical construction materials included Natural Stone and Mudbrick; both are locally sourced materials. Different building typologies are present in this area, and traditional courtyard house typologies are concentrated at the historic core of the city, mainly in the “Jewish quarter”. Handicrafts were used to build small accommodations and venues.

Figure 28 buildings finished with original stone and brickwork, highlighting traditional construction methods, Source: (A.R.S.progetti, 2014)

Figure 29 original parapets, railings, and window grills in wrought iron or masonry, common features in traditional architecture, Source: (A.R.S.progetti, 2014)

The Jewish neighborhood in Duhok City Center is characterized by its traditional architecture that reflects the cultural and historical identity of the city. The preservation and rehabilitation of these structures will protect the city's traditional urban fabric while maintaining its cultural significance.

4.3. Research Methodology

The study aims to explore the interaction between urban design elements and their impact on human perceptual and emotional experience. Research objectives 1 and 2 were addressed by collecting primary and secondary data, while the 3rd objective of the research was an outcome of the triangulation of these data. By integrating the results of primary data from the questionnaire and secondary data from the related theories, concepts, and similar studies, the final objective of the research was addressed, as depicted in Figure 30.

Figure 30 Research Methodology Structure, Source: Developed by Research

4.4. Data Collection Methods

4.4.1. Semi-Structured Questionnaire

The Semi-structured questionnaire is a research tool that combines qualitative and quantitative data collection. Open-ended questions were used for collecting Perceptual responses to environment Visual stimuli, which are known for being less guided, to provide insights that could be missed with closed-ended questions, and the analysis of these responses can help understand how individuals reason about important aspects in built environments that are shaped by their perceptions (Ferrario and Stantcheva, 2022). Multiple-choice questions as shown in Appendix A) were used to collect Narrative data perceptual responses and to gather specific demographic information and preferences for urban elements.

Emotional Responses to Visual Stimuli were collected in an abbreviated PANAS scale to assess the emotional responses of participants to different visual stimuli in urban environments. They were asked to rate their emotions evoked by the stimuli given in the first few seconds, like joy, interest, stress, and frustration after viewing images of urban settings.

4.4.2. Abbreviated PANAS (The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule)

The PANAS was developed in 1988 by psychologists David Watson, Lee Anna Clark, and Auke Tellegen (Mulder, 2018) the scale was frequently used in self-report emotional responses in literature. Clinical studies, as well as non-clinical ones, have found PANAS to be a valid and reliable assessment tool for measuring positive and negative effects (Merz et al., 2013).

Emotions can range from 10 to 50 for both the Positive and Negative affect (Watson, D., Clark, L. A., & Tellegen, A., 1988). Four basic mood categories as illustrated in Figure 31 were developed based on the PANAS model by Watson and Tellegen (1985), with examples of moods (in the circle) from Russell (1980) and Barrett & Russell (1999) (Desmet et al., 2012, Kuppens et al., 2013).

Figure 31 PANAS Wheel of Emotions source: (Watson and Tellegen, 1985, Brdar, 2020)

A simple abbreviated scale of PANAS was utilized to analyze and capture emotions as a response to visual stimuli, (Watson and Tellegen, 1985) The developers of PANAS acknowledged that the scale can be modified to better fit the main objectives of the research. Such as focusing on fewer emotions that are more likely to be influenced by the context of the study (Zsidó, 2024). When researchers are interested in the emotional impact of visual stimuli, they often select emotions that can capture the nuances of how individuals react to what they perceive.

This is reflected in Tuan's (1977) work on space and place, where the emotional resonance of a place is tied to specific, culturally or contextually relevant emotions. Relevant emotions to the context of the study, as shown in Table 4, include joy, pride, stress, and inspiration. Positive emotions are linked to well-designed, culturally resonant spaces, while negative emotions like stress or fear stem from poor design or danger. Tools like PANAS measure these emotional responses, helping planners and architects design environments that evoke positive emotions while mitigating negative ones.

Table 4 Emotions Triggered by Visual Stimuli in Built Environments

Relevant Emotions	Their occurrence in response to environmental stimuli
Joyful	Associated with spaces promoting leisure, beauty, and social interaction. (Li et al., 2022)
Relaxed	Tied to environments featuring natural elements. (Grahm et al., 2010)
Excited	Spaces that evoke a sense of novelty, and engagement (Wagener et al., 2022)
Stressed	Triggered by overcrowded, noisy, or visually cluttered spaces (Gatersleben et al., 2017)
Upset/Frustrated	Arise in environments that feel uncomfortable, and inaccessible (Ellin, 1997)
Ashamed	associated with feelings of disrepair or neglect (Weijs-Perrée et al., 2020)
Scared	Elicited by environments that feel unsafe due to poor lighting, isolation, and visible danger (Burns, 2000)
Proud	spaces that reflect cultural or community identity (Knez et al., 2018)
Inspired	Triggered by aesthetically beautiful or innovative design(Desai and Psychology, 2024)
Interest	Often sparked by unique, innovative, or culturally significant spaces (Dzebic, 2018)

The abbreviated scale endured through a panel of experts review for its reliability and accuracy of use as in Table 5, experts were from academic and non-academic fields of Psychology and Psychiatry. A detailed report was developed for the measurement tools of data collection that were utilized in this study to collect Perceptual and emotional responses as referred to in Appendix B.

Table 5 Experts list for Scale accuracy and validity

Expert Name	Position	Affiliation
Perjan Hashim Taha	Professor Dr. of Psychiatry	Psychiatry Unit, College of Medicine, University of Duhok
Chachan Jumaa Mohammed	Professor Dr. of Psychology	Psychology unit, Basic Education department, University of Duhok
Mohammed Saeed Mohammed	Professor of Psychology	Psychology unit, Basic Education department, University of Duhok
Salim Al-Hakim	Assistant Professor, Dr. of Psychiatry	Psychiatry Unit, College of Medicine, University of Duhok
Radwan Sadeeq Saeed	Lecturer, Ph.D. in Psychology	Psychology unit, Basic Education department, University of Duhok

4.4.3. Semi-Structured Interviews

A semi-structured interview is a chain of open-ended questions based on the contents the researcher wants to cover. In this research, two forms of interviews were made for both government experts and property owners of the study area.

To gain insights from experts and stakeholders regarding the challenges and hierarchy of implementation plans. Historians, architects, cultural experts, psychologists, residents, and stakeholders. Semi-structured interviews were conducted, recorded, and transcribed for thematic analysis.

4.5. Sampling Selection and Size

This study utilized Non-probability Sampling, specifically the Purposive Sampling method, to ensure that the sample precisely illustrates the demographic characteristics and background relevant to research objectives (Rai and Thapa, 2015). This approach was selected to keep precision in assessing the impact of built environment design on the perceptual and emotional experiences of a young adult with at least a bachelor's degree in education. This method involves the non-random selection of participants based on predefined criteria, allowing researchers to easily collect initial data relevant to the study's objectives.

4.5.1. Sample Size Calculation

The sample size calculated for the study focused on specific age groups between 20-34 years old to minimize the impact of personal background, age factor, and experiences on the collected data as shown in Table 6. According to the literature previously mentioned in Chapter 3, these factors can influence humans' perception and emotions, to ensure the accuracy and reliability of Data.

Table 6 The age group distribution and number (NationalStatisticsBureau, 2022)

Age Group	Female	Male	Total
20-24	18,341	17,428	35,770
25-29	15,791	15,066	30,857
30-34	13,940	13,365	27,306

The study targeted a specific segment of the Duhok population, aged 20-34 with an educational background, that encompasses 93,933 individuals of the total population of Duhok Governorate of 450,000 (NationalStatisticsBureau, 2022). The considered parameters were set at 5% for the margin of error, and a confidence level commonly used in various research fields of 90% is expected to be the accuracy of responses (Taherdoost and Systems, 2017). The proportion of the population is set at 20%, reflecting the population aged 20-34. Based on inputs, the recommended sample size was calculated to be approximately 173 samples as shown in Table 7.

Table 7 The parameters and Values for calculating the Sample Size of the study.

Parameter	Value
Confidence Level (Z)	90% (Z-value = 1.645)
Response Distribution (p)	20% (0.2)
Margin of Error (e)	5% (0.05)
Initial Sample Size (n)	173
Population Size (N)	450,000
Adjusted Sample Size (n_adj)	173

The initial sample size (n) is calculated by using the formula by (Kotrlík et al., 2001) as illustrated below for the proportion-based survey:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1 - p)}{e^2}$$

$$n = \frac{(1.645)^2 \cdot 0.2 \cdot (1 - 0.2)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{2.705025 \cdot 0.2 \cdot 0.8}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{0.432804}{0.0025} = 173.12 \approx 173$$

Only 170 responses were selected due to the negligence of criteria in responses, Data with incomplete responses, or inaccurate answers were neglected. By addressing these issues in collecting data, accuracy of information and reliability were delivered.

4.5.2. Participant Selection Criteria

Participants were selected based on the following criteria: Educational Background and age of the Participants will be selected within a specific age range relevant to the study. Participants will be chosen to have a similar cultural background to ensure consistency in the data related to cultural perceptions influenced by cultural heritage and values.

These criteria ensure that the selected participants have homogeneous knowledge, cultural background, and relevant experiences to provide consistent insights into the research questions.

4.6. Data Analysis Methods

The collected data were analyzed using both qualitative and quantitative methods, and responses from interviews and open-ended questionnaire items were coded and thematically analyzed to identify key themes and Emotional data insights in Simple Content Analysis as follows:

4.6.1. Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis was employed in the study as a qualitative research tool to examine participants' perceptual reactions to certain visual stimuli. According to (Braun and Clarke, 2006) This kind of analysis is frequently used to gather psychological data, such as perceptual responses and experiences. From the viewpoints of the participants, it offers insights into investigations of complex phenomena and can go through the following analytical steps:

- Data Collection: Collecting non-numeric or qualitative research data using narrative analysis and descriptive perceptions.
- Data familiarization: familiarizing yourself with data by reviewing and highlighting the main ideas elaborated by the respondents.
- Coding: Identifying and labeling the main key terms and patterns within the collected data.
- Thematic Analysis: Grouping codes into broader themes that capture significant aspects of the data.

- Interpretation: Analyze the themes to understand their implications and the deeper meanings they convey.
- Presentation: Communicating the findings clearly and compellingly, often through detailed narratives and visual representations.

4.6.2. Quantitative Data Analysis

Data from demographic information, multiple-choice questions, and self-reported emotions were statistically analyzed and represented in analytical diagrams like “Bar Charts, Pie Charts, and Radar Charts”.

The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) was later used to categorize these emotions based on the frequency of occurrence of each quadrant shown in the PANAS wheel of emotions. Positive affect refers to the propensity to experience positive emotions and interact with others positively. Negative affect, on the other hand, involves experiencing the world more negatively. The emotions were distributed into relevant quadrants as depicted in Table 8.

Table 8 Data quadrant representation, summarizing the categorized emotions into relevant quadrants:

Quadrant	Related Emotions
Calm-Pleasant	Joyful, Proud, Inspired, Relaxed
Energized-Pleasant	Interested, Excited
Energized-Unpleasant	Stressed, Upset, and Frustrated
Calm-Unpleasant	Scared, Ashamed

4.6.2.1. Analysis Of Emotional Quadrants

The categorization of emotions is based on four quadrants, from the pleasure and energy received from the group of emotions people experience when exposed to different environments.

- **Calm-Unpleasant:** This quadrant indicates a lack of engagement and a vibrant environment. Research suggests that this quadrant appears in Urban spaces that lack human dimensions, where patterns of Sadness and Anger are more common (Wang et al., 2023).

- **Energized-Unpleasant:** Spaces that evoke this quadrant of emotions mostly refer to spaces lacking social control. That can create tension and discomfort in reflecting unwanted behaviors (Savic and Savicic, 2014).
- **Calm-Pleasant:** areas that stimulate pleasant but low-energy emotions may be categorized as tranquil environments. Such as green parks or quiet spaces. these spaces can foster relaxation but lack social interaction and desire (Nenko and Petrova, 2019).
- **Energized-Pleasant:** The quadrant represents Vibrant and engaging urban spaces that can promote positive emotional experiences and enhance social interaction. Urban Centers often exhibit these patterns, where happiness and excitement are spatially concentrated (Nenko and Petrova, 2019, Wang et al., 2023).

In General, the methodological insights can contribute to the understanding of emotional and perceptual responses in urban environments and can further pave the way for future research to explore the intricate relationship between human well-being and the built environment.

Table 9 below highlights the Data need indicators and the purpose of the collected data to address the three research questions based on the research methodological insights.

Research Question	Data Needed Indicator
How does the urban built environment in Duhok City Center impact human emotions and perception?	Perceptual and Emotional responses to visual stimuli
What physical elements of urban design enhance human perceptual and emotional experiences in the Duhok built environment?	Identification of specific urban elements from literature and further assessment in the Duhok city context from perceptual responses that identify the main and sub-elements.
How do human-environment interactions contribute to humanizing public spaces in Duhok city?	Qualitative feedback and a new generating model for the interaction with urban spaces

CHAPTER FIVE FINDINGS AND RESULTS

5. Overview

The chapter discusses the findings and results of each method used to achieve the aims and objectives of the research. Starting with assessing the study area from the Lens of the human-centered approach. Further, there are the results of interpretation and visualization from the semi-structured questionnaires distributed among the residents of Duhok City. The results are discussed and analyzed to develop a new model for designing and planning the built environments that have positive impacts on the human state of mind.

5.1. Interview findings

This section includes different aspects and insights collected from experts' interviews, including the City Center and Master Plan, Challenges in heritage conservation, city center planning Current State of the Heritage Conservation Plan, the Implementing phase of the Duhok City Center Masterplan, and Insights from Expert Interviews on Perceptual and Emotional Responses to Urban Environments.

5.1.1. City Center master plan perspective for natural and cultural resources

In an interview conducted by the researcher to understand the current plans for the historic urban environment and the progress of related projects, the Head of the Heritage and Antiquities Department in Duhok stated that the General Masterplan offers a broad strategy for the entire city of Duhok, although it does not provide specific recommendations for the City Centre area. In May 2013, the Governorate of Duhok requested a team of specific companies to submit a financial and technical proposal for the development of Duhok City Center's detailed design. ARS Progetti Spa was granted the project in June 2013.

The primary goal of the project was to create a comprehensive plan for the City Centre of Duhok, which included specific guidelines for heritage conservation, architectural design, land use, plot coverage, and façade materials, as well as allowances for parking, green spaces, and unoccupied plots.

The advantage of this project is that it focuses on improving and generating new perspectives on important natural and cultural resources. Moreover, the objective is to restore and conserve heritage assets that reflect significant aspects of the City's historical evolution. Preservation and conservation of heritage is an important aspect of planning, specifically in cities with rich historical and cultural backgrounds. Duhok City is considered one of the cities that has rich history and heritage sites. There were valuable insights obtained from another interview with the head of the planning section in the planning department in Duhok regarding the conservation endeavors for historic and heritage assets in Duhok City. Stated that the implementation of the masterplan objectives has faced many struggles in the execution stages one of them being the rejection of Duhok residents to follow the plan's objectives and guidelines due to economic barriers, they also presented extensive data

Figure 32 City Center Zoning plan highlighted for Modern and traditional areas, Source:(A.R.S.progetti, 2014)

and research derived from a plan developed by an Italian corporation in 2016. This comprehensive strategy, targeting the downtown area of the city, was scheduled to be executed in 2017. The Italian organization conducted thorough field assessments utilizing maps, GIS, and direct observations, involving specialized teams of architects, planners, and other relevant professionals. In Figure 32, the blue-shaded areas are planned as traditional parts to be conserved, the others are modern areas.

The initial phase involved detailed data collection and analysis of the city center, identifying and highlighting significant heritage sites. The plan also delineated zones for various purposes, including parking lots, open and green spaces, places for mixed-use development, cultural preservation sites, and traditional souk areas. This comprehensive plan aimed to enhance the city's structure and preserve its heritage.

5.1.2. Insights from Expert Interviews on Perceptual and Emotional Responses to Urban Environments

Insights were gathered from professionals in Human Psychology regarding assessing the perception and emotional state of people. In the process of developing a comprehensive methodology for evaluating the impact of urban environmental design on the human state of mind, two semi-structured interviews were conducted with a psychiatrist and a psychologist. Both experts emphasized the insightful effect of the environment on the human mood and emotional state. The experts further supported the importance of investigating this interaction between the environment and human well-being, which can also support the psychological healing process when designing thoughtful and therapeutic spaces.

methodological considerations for data collection and analysis were provided by the field experts, and exposure and interaction were given importance when studying a specific environmental influence. When studying perception, open-ended questions were suggested for data collection in terms of perceptual responses. To gather a broader range of perceptual experiences pre-defined responses were recommended to be avoided.

This method can give a broader range of data that can be diverse when it comes to personal experience, cultural background, and individual perspectives. For more accurate information in psychological studies, immediate and instinctive reactions were suggested to be gathered to provide spontaneous data when exposed to stimuli. Emotional data collection can be for clinical or non-clinical purposes. The experts discussed the use of comprehensive tools like SAM or PANAS, which measure a broad range of emotions and their intensity to identify a specific mental state, in-depth emotional assessment, or psychological issues often in therapeutic or research contexts, that are not related to their exposure to specific settings. For non-clinical purposes, it was recommended to use a simplified approach with a minimum set of emotions as earlier highlighted in Chapter 3. This approach is suitable for researchers aiming to understand general emotional responses to specific stimuli, rather than conducting in-depth clinical evaluations.

The gathered insights were crucial in generating the methodology for this study. Integrating those recommendations, open-ended questions, the capture of immediate responses, and the non-clinical purpose approach were considered in creating the data

collection tools. The research is intended to offer a comprehensive analysis of how different environmental settings influence well-being.

5.2. Findings and Results from the Questionnaire

This section will discuss the questionnaire results on how various urban environments in Duhok City can affect residents' well-being. It will cover participants' perceptions, emotions, and preferences. This result will provide a comprehensive understanding of the psychological effect of urban design, specifically in terms of historic, green, and narrative environments. This section will further investigate the correlation between urban environments and residents' state of mind. By analyzing these data, we can highlight the most important urban features, which are strongly involved with a positive mental state. This analysis should help prioritize urban elements for a more human city design. Thematic insights are tackled from open-ended responses to capture the qualitative aspects of people's experience within the urban environments in Duhok City, as they were expressed in participants' own words freely with no restrictions. The findings from this section will highlight the importance of considering residents' perceptions, emotions, and experiences in urban planning and design practices.

5.3. Socio-demographic background of respondents

This section provides the socio-demographic background of participants. The questionnaire was given to participants of both genders, male and female, within the age group of 20 to 34 years who reside in Duhok. In addition, participants were selected from different educational and knowledgeable backgrounds.

5.3.1. Gender Distribution of Survey Respondents

In this study, the questionnaires were distributed to both males and females in Duhok City. The chart titled "Gender Distribution of Respondents" depicted in Figure 33, visually represents the proportion of male and female respondents who participated in the survey, based on a total of 170 respondents.

Figure 33 Gender Distribution of Survey respondents, source: Researcher constructed

The chart shows that females constitute a larger portion of the respondents, with 66% being female participants, while male participants make up 34% of the respondents. This approach to sampling helps produce meaningful data and provides insights into the perspectives of both genders in the Duhok City center, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the community's views since gender does not impact the perception.

5.3.2. Age Distribution of Respondents

The pie chart labeled "Age Distribution" offers a perceptive analysis of the age composition of the research participants.

Figure 34 Age Distribution of the respondents, source: Researcher constructed.

The data indicated in Figure 34 shows that 41% of the participants fall within the age range of 20-24, while 33% are in the age group of 25-29, and 26% within the age group of 30-34. Consequently, the majority of individuals we examined fall into the category of young adults, specifically in the age range of their mid-twenties to early thirties. By acknowledging this age distribution, we gain insight into the distinct requirements and affective responses of this group, which is crucial for creating urban settings that fully connect with them. By directing our attention toward the human experiences of this dominant demographic, we can gain a deeper understanding of how urban design influences their day-to-day existence and overall state of being.

5.3.3. Educational background of the participants

It is essential to consider the educational background of respondents to analyze perceptions regarding urban surroundings. This study aims to investigate the impact of different elements of the built environment on human perception and emotions. By incorporating participants with diverse educational backgrounds, the study can achieve an extensive understanding of these factors, as distinct fields of study contribute to distinct perspectives and experiences. The use of this approach is crucial in cross-disciplinary studies, as cultural and personal experiences have a substantial impact on the realization of perceptions.

Figure 35 The distribution of the educational background of respondents

Figure 35 indicates the distribution of the educational background of the respondents, the majority of respondents are bachelor's degree holders which is equivalent to 62% of participants, while 25% have master's Degrees in different fields, 10% are high school graduates, while only 1% refer to the Doctorate, and 2% other backgrounds that weren't specified. The results highlight that the majority of respondents are bachelor's degree holders while the minimum are Doctorates.

5.4. Perceptions of Historic Urban Environments

Perceptions of Historic Urban Environments were collected based on the provided responses, the following thematic analysis framework was generated, as depicted in Table 11. The emotional and perceptual responses to the historic urban environment have been categorized into distinct themes and sub-themes. Each theme reflects a unique aspect of the participants' perceptions and emotional connections with the historic urban landscape. The analysis follows the steps of selecting quotations, identifying keywords, coding, generating themes, and conceptualizing the findings.

Table 10 below shows the Themes that occurred in the participant responses, it includes the coding groups generated for each theme and the frequency or percentage of occurrence of each theme.

Table 9 Thematic analysis and coding in Response to Historic Urban Environment

Theme	Coding	Frequency	Percentage
Heritage and History	Old/Ancient, Historical /History, Kurdish heritage, Heritage, Historical Building Preservation/Conservation, Remnants, Historic Landmark, History and Culture, Roots, Historic City	142	35.6%
Neglect and Abandonment	Neglected/Abandoned, Overgrown, Lost Spirit, Damaged	34	8.5%
Beauty and Aesthetics	Beautiful/Beauty, Charming, Authentic/Authenticity, Cozy, Rustic, Rustic Charm, Earthy, Natural Materials	54	13.5%
Emotional Connection	Nostalgia/Nostalgic, Memories, sadness/Sadness, Peace/Peaceful, Childhood, feeling/Emotions, Love, Livelihood, Warm, Spirit, Spiritual/Spirituality, Heartwarming, Peaceful, reminiscence, Tranquility, Homeland, Simple Life	74	18.5%

Theme	Coding	Frequency	Percentage
Preservation and Conservation	Preservation/Conservation, Investment Needed, Preservation Needed, Restoration	19	4.8%
Architectural Elements	Architecture, Architectural Details, Traditional Design, Stone, Windows, Iron-Barred Windows, Arches, small windows, arched doorways	28	6.8%
Nature and Environment	Natural/Nature, Environment/Environmental, Green, Earthy, natural materials, nature born	15	3.5%
Cultural Aspects	Culture/Cultural, Kurdish/Kurdistan, Civilization, Identity	28	7.0%
Human Scale	Human Scale, Approachable, Intimate, Dimensions, Simplicity, Human Proportions	7	1.8%

The questionnaire participants were asked an open-ended question to describe the Historic Urban Environment in the Jewish neighborhood as illustrated in Figure 36, within the case study area in Duhok City Center, based on an image provided.

Figure 36 Historic Urban Environment representing Jewish neighbourhood in Duhok city centre

There were no constraints or choices available that would allow individuals to express and describe based on their experiences and backgrounds.

The responses underwent full revision and systematic analysis to produce coding. Consequently, newfound themes were acquired, as shown in Figure 37, to encapsulate participants' interpretations of the presented image.

Figure 37 Bar chart representing the frequency of themes that occurred in responses, Researcher constructed.

As a result, there was a comprehensive description of emotions, memories, aesthetic appeal, and various other aspects of the urban environment. This highlighted a significant interest in historical sites.

The generated themes for understanding the perception of respondents toward the historic urban environment indicated an essential embodiment of the cultural identity and heritage value. Those environments were perceived as living connections to the past that evoked affective responses like “Nostalgia” and “pride” that presented a strong emotional attachment and belonging.

Thematic Exploration of Perceptions in Historic Urban Contexts was categorized into the following themes generated from open-ended questions:

5.4.1. Historical Value and Cultural Aspects

The theme that emerged most frequently in responses when describing their perception. There was a significant awareness of the value that people place in their historic urban environment, which is seen as deeply rooted in the cultural identity and heritage of the participants. The heritage and historical value theme reflect the respondents’ realization and awareness of the value that people find when they perceive historical environments. The theme that emerged most frequently in the responses was an awareness of the

significant value that people place on their historic urban environments, which are seen as deeply rooted in the cultural identity and heritage of the survey participants. The terms "heritage," "history," and "roots" are mentioned in 36% to emphasize the importance of these sites as embodiments of the community's collective past and everlasting historical connections. The cultural significance was also highlighted at 7% through words like "Kurdish Heritage," "Cultural Heritage," and "Ancient". Individuals articulated that:

“History and culture in the picture, that feels warm, love, and a long journey of human history in our land.”

“It shows that Duhok city has a good history, continues civilization and living of ancestors, beautiful heritage, and pride.”

These statements express a deep admiration and strong emotional bond to the heritage and cultural aspects of the provided picture. It emphasizes the emotional reaction they experienced towards the historical surroundings using terms such as feeling warmth and love. The reference to the "long journey of human history" emphasizes the significance and lasting nature of the heritage sites in the area. This denotes the buildings' cultural significance, reflecting their role in shaping and maintaining a sense of identity and pride among the respondents. Furthermore, it highlights the importance of heritage buildings as symbols of civilization and cultural heritage. It suggests that these elements are essential to shaping their identity and improving their sense of place to achieve human-city criteria.

“It's so heartwarming, it reminds me of my origin!”

“Beauty of heritage that represents city's identity and culture”

These statements demonstrate a deep emotional connection and sense of pride associated with the cultural aspects of historic places, highlighting their influence on participants' collective and individual identities. The respondents remarked that the historic urban environment created feelings of nostalgia and a sense of belonging. This suggests that its significance goes beyond its tangible features, encompassing its cultural value and historical continuity, which in turn enhances community pride and cultural identity. Hence, the preservation of the historic environment is vital for preserving the community's emotional well-being, following Maslow's hierarchy of needs, which encompasses self-actualization and self-transcendence.

The word cloud analysis, shown in Figure 38, indicates the frequency of mentioned terms perceived by participants regarding the Heritage, history, and cultural aspects.

Figure 38 Word Cloud analysis, representing historical and cultural aspect's themes

The word cloud indicates that the perception of heritage and historical significance is deeply rooted in the historical continuity and cultural identity of the community and is essential to the cultural fabric of the city.

5.4.1.1. Emotional Connection

The frequent use of affective language indicates that these structures evoke strong individual and collective emotions. The terms "nostalgia," "memories," as well as "childhood" were expressed in 19% of the results that emphasize human attachments embedded in these places. The emotional reactions highlight the buildings' significance in the cultural and social fabric of the community:

“Childhood memories, peaceful time, Stones, alley, nature”

“Old buildings and houses with hundreds of people's memories”

“Somewhere full of kindness and love, with lovely people living in”

The quotes represent a response to the perceived historical environment, generating a nostalgic and serene interpretation of childhood memories. This highlights an important emotional connection to the past, emphasizing how the physical surroundings, specifically the built heritage, contribute to a sense of tranquility and pleasant memories of events. Furthermore, it implies that the environment provides not only aesthetic appeal

but also an enhanced feeling of emotional connection experienced by its users. The word cloud in Figure 39, shows that respondents' emotional experiences like “childhood memories”, “pride” and “nostalgic” strongly influence their perception regarding historic urban environments. Individuals had significant sentimental value. This indicates that respondents value emotional and memory-triggering effects.

Figure 39 Word Cloud analysis, representing Emotional Connection themes

As a result, the heritage develops a human-friendly environment and improves the place's perception, which indicates that these human elements are essential to the city's identity and attractiveness, particularly enhancing the community's collective memories and overall emotional well-being.

5.4.1.2. Neglect and Abandonment, a Call for Preservation

The participants perceived the value of historic environments, yet the current state of these places is a source of concern for many respondents, who have brought attention to the problems of neglect and decay. Words like "damaged," "abandoned," and "neglected" express about 9% as an impression of loss of the city's heritage and the need for immediate action. While less common, a clear call for conservation and preservation indicates a focused concern among the respondents. This theme emphasizes the importance of taking proactive steps towards preserving these structures, thus assuring their preservation as a valuable part of the community's heritage for future generations.

“Historical records that can be preserved, conserved, and utilized again.”

People emphasized the significance of safeguarding, conserving, and utilizing those historical documents. This statement demonstrates a proactive approach to the management of heritage sites, acknowledging their value as valuable resources that can be revitalized for future generations as well. The frequent mention of the perceived current state of neglect and abandonment indicates a significant concern among respondents. This is evident in the word cloud, depicted in Figure 40, where terms such as "Preservation," "disrepair," and "abandoned" were commonly used. This suggests a high level of awareness regarding the deteriorating condition of the historical sites.

Figure 40 Word Cloud analysis representing Neglect and Abandonment themes

The emphasis on preservation indicates a dedication to safeguarding those sites from additional decay and destruction, while also utilizing them for the city's future development. This approach not only preserves the historic sites but also incorporates them into the current and future urban context of the city, ensuring that the built heritage continues to be a functional and integral part of the city's cultural and built heritage.

5.4.1.3. The Beauty and Aesthetic Value of Architectural Elements

According to the respondents, this theme represents the perceived visual and aesthetic appeal. The use of adjectives such as "beautiful," "charming," and "authentic" suggests a fondness for the structures' traditional and natural features. This appreciation for the buildings' aesthetic value highlights the significance of preserving those unique features and integrating them into new development. An understanding and admiration of the buildings' design elements was shown by mentioning particular architectural details. The historical and aesthetic importance of the buildings was enhanced by the respondents'

appreciation for traditional designs and materials, specifically the word “Stone” which was frequently mentioned. Other words like “Architecture, Architectural Details, Traditional Design, Windows, Iron-Barred Windows, Arches, small windows, arched doorways” were the visual elements impacting the perception of the respondents.

“Remnants that have become art”

“I appreciate the architectural and historical significance of the buildings. They exhibit a rustic charm and tell a story of the area's past. The stone construction and traditional design elements, such as arched doorways and iron-barred windows, are characteristic of historic architecture and contribute to the unique aesthetic of the place. The buildings' current state of disrepair also adds a layer of authenticity and historical context, reflecting their age and the passage of time.”

A profound respect for the architectural value of those structures is emphasized by the quotation, which refers to their rustic charm that narrates the city's history. In addition to the traditional elements mentioned and the building's stone construction, which contribute to the unique aesthetic of the place, the building's current state of despair emphasizes its authenticity and historical context, reflecting the city's continued existence.

This adds to the building's charm and the narrative richness of the city. The word cloud, shown below in Figure 41, represents the dominant words elaborated by participants which affected their perceptions of the historic built environments.

Figure 41 Word Cloud analysis, representing Beauty and Aesthetic Value themes

Overall, the data indicates that the community places great importance on the aesthetic and historical significance of these architectural elements, as well as their integration into the historic identity and character of the built environment.

5.4.1.4. Natural integration and human scale

A harmonious relationship between the built and natural environments is suggested by 4% of responses for the integration of natural elements and the environment with the buildings, which was greatly perceived by participants. The significance of biophilic design principles in historic structures was highlighted in this theme.

“a beautiful mix of nature and historical buildings that should be conserved”

“Using nature and natural materials to build houses”

These quotes illustrate how the respondent perceived the aesthetic and cultural value of the natural and historical structures integrating in perfect harmony. It promotes future development that harmonizes buildings with the natural environment by utilizing sustainable construction methods and preserving this integration. The importance of nature-integrating building practices has been highlighted, and there is a call to preserve these historic structures within their natural surroundings. The infrequent occurrence but notable emphasis on the “human scale” indicates that respondents deeply value the relatability of these structures. The buildings' simplicity and human proportions create an apparent contradiction with modern constructions, emphasizing a preference for more human-friendly designs, as conveyed by the quotes below.

“What stands out to me is the human scale and how close to nature

the material is than its modern counterparts.”

The concept of human scale is essential in the creation of user-friendly environments. It involves designing buildings and spaces that are proportionate to human dimensions, thus ensuring that these environments are more inviting and comfortable for human use. The theme of creating spaces that promote attachment and a sense of belonging to users is essential, as indicated by Maslow's hierarchy of human needs (Sosteric, 2019). This theme is supported by the literature review, which suggests that environments designed on a human scale contribute to positive emotional responses and overall well-being. (Sussman & Hollander, 2021).

The participants frequently mentioned natural materials such as "stone" as they blend harmoniously with the surroundings and evoke a sense of authenticity and continuity with the past. This principle follows the concept of biophilic design, which promotes the incorporation of natural materials and design elements into constructed environments to improve the overall well-being of humans (Kellert, Heerwagen, & Mador, 2011). The word cloud in Figure 42 represents the dominant words influencing perception.

Figure 42 Word Cloud analysis, representing Natural integration and human scale themes

Therefore, the importance of embracing human scale and nature integration in the design of urban environments is consistent with the conclusions drawn from existing literature. This highlights the essential role it plays in improving the emotional experience of individuals by maintaining the cultural and environmental integration of built heritage.

In summary, the findings of this section focus on the prevailing sentiment regarding the perception of Historic urban environments that make them visually attractive and evoke highly positive emotional attachment and engagement. This emphasizes the significance of conserving and integrating historical elements in the process of urban planning for new developments and designs. This is crucial to maintain the cultural and aesthetic value of the city's history.

5.4.2. Emotional response to historic built environment

The state of mind towards urban environments has a significant impact on how humans perceive and experience emotions and overall well-being. This section examines the emotional responses of the participants towards historic built environments, utilizing the

Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS), to measure the positive and negative effects. The participants' emotional response was evaluated using a range of emotions, including Upset, Stressed, Frustrated, Interested, Ashamed, Proud, Excited, Scared, Relaxed, inspired, and Joyful.

Consequently, there was a notable positive emotional response observed towards the historical environment. The historic built environments were predominantly associated with positive emotions such as "relaxed," "interested," "proud," "inspired," and "joyful," while negative emotions like "upset" or "ashamed" were rarely expressed, as shown in Figure 43.

Figure 43 Bar Chart representing emotions toward Historic Urban Environment

The results of the Historic built environment are shown in the radar charts below (see Figure 44).

Figure 44 Radar Chart analysis, Representing the Emotional Quadrant in response to Historic Urban Environment

The responses demonstrate that people's emotions were categorized into two quadrant settings, as shown by the "Calm-pleasant" and "Energized-pleasant" quadrants, which indicate that the historic built environment is more likely to evoke positive affective responses.

The wide variation in emotional responses of participants underscores the psychological benefits of historical urban environments that improve human health. The demonstration in Fig 45 in a poll asked participants to evaluate the statement "Historical buildings and environments contribute to human mental well-being." Approximately 70% of respondents strongly agreed with this.

Figure 45 The impact of Historic built environment on the Well-being of Respondents

(Sun et al., 2021) reported similar observations in their experiments that studied human perception of both traditional and modern commercial districts using EEG. The results captured a positive subjective evaluation of traditional compared to modern districts in terms of relaxation and comfort. In contrast, the findings obtained by (Sektani et al., 2021) indicated that individuals without architectural expertise or knowledge exhibited a preference for modern buildings over heritage buildings in Erbil city.

The findings cannot be generalized due to differences in cultural context, as a variation in perception is attributed to differences in the personal experiences of respondents, their cultural background, or other specific criteria associated with the study of modern and historic environments, which is indicated by Rapoport and Hawkes (1970). These discoveries can be applied in future urban planning to enhance users' emotional experience and to improve their overall mental well-being. Ultimately, will create a more humane city.

5.5. Perception of the natural environment in urban space design

This section explores how respondents perceive natural environments in urban spaces, as shown in Figure 46.

Figure 46 Natural Urban Environment representing Hi Park in Duhok city centre

The results focus on the impact on the human state of mind in terms of well-being, aesthetic appreciation, and functionality. The findings highlight the important role of natural elements in enhancing the quality of urban space design. This analysis illustrates a qualitative method to provide insights into how those elements contribute to the positive emotional experience of residents. By analyzing the responses, a comprehensive understanding of perceived benefits was tackled to highlight the importance of integrating natural environment design.

The natural urban environment is crucial for the city's aesthetic and the quality of urban life. This thematic analysis explores how different aspects of natural settings were perceived by respondents. There was a focus on themes related to natural elements, tranquility and relaxation, aesthetic aspects, historical significance, and practical uses as shown in Table 11. Understanding these perspectives can help designers create urban spaces that promote community well-being and meet the needs of residents.

Table 10 Thematic analysis and coding in Response to Natural Urban Environment

Theme	Keywords	Frequency	Percentage
Natural Elements	green, nature, trees, greenery, view, scenery, sky, weather, water, fountain, pool	150	37.0%
Tranquility and Relaxation	relaxed, calm, peaceful, tranquility, joyful, energized, refreshed, mental state, happiness	60	14.8%
Aesthetic and Social Value	beautiful, nice, enjoyable, lovely, good, excellent, community, events, social, functional	105	25.9%
Historical and Cultural Significance	traditional, historical, heritage, authentic, stone, buildings, specific features	50	12.3%
Cleanliness and Maintenance	clean, well-maintained, neat	10	2.5%
Suggestions for Improvement	more greenery, more seating, more water features, enhance, average, normal, not attractive, suggestions, improvements	30	7.4%
Practical Uses	walk, garden, recreational, exercise	10	2.5%
Environmental Concerns	pollution, artificial, unnatural	20	4.9%

The bar chart in Figure 47 illustrates the questionnaire results showing the frequency of each theme regarding participants' perception of the natural urban settings.

Figure 47 Bar Chart representing the frequency of themes that occurred in responses, Researcher constructed.

It shows that natural elements are the most valued with a frequency of (37%), followed by aesthetic and social value with a frequency of (25.9%), and Tranquility and relaxation (14.8%). Historical and cultural significance (12.3%) and environmental concerns (4.9%), also notable but less commonly occurred were the cleanliness and maintenance, practical uses, and suggestions for improvement.

5.5.1. Thematic Exploration of Perceptions in Natural Urban Contexts

This section highlights the categorized themes generated from open-ended questions to study the perception of the Natural Urban Environment.

5.5.1.1. Natural elements

Natural features add to the aesthetic and quality of the urban environment. According to respondents, this theme was the most commonly stated, representing 37% of responses. This finding demonstrates that green features have a significant impact on participants' perceptions, as related words occurred in 150 responses. This shows that natural features are essential for creating visually appealing and engaging surroundings for residents. Statements like "a beautiful scene with lots of greenery" emphasize the necessity of integrating diverse natural elements into urban design to improve the overall user experience.

Figure 48 Word Cloud analysis for Natural elements that are perceived by participants

The word cloud in Figure 48 illustrates the frequency of words mentioned in the participants' responses. The occurrence of the words “Trees”, “Water features” and “Green” was the most dominant codes that occurred in the theme of natural elements. The frequent mention of natural components indicates people's perceptions of the role of nature in nurturing a link between humans and the environment. The preferences of individuals regarding the choice between two groups of photos labeled A and B.

Group A, which comprises 3 pictures of man-made elements, was preferred by approximately 33% of the respondents. In contrast, Group B, featuring 3 photos of man-made elements, was favored by 67% of the respondents. This significant majority indicates a clear preference for the natural elements. The chart in Figure 49, suggests most of respondents preferred the elements depicted in Group B, which can be interpreted as a preference for natural materials over man-made ones. This preference indicates a strong inclination towards natural elements in the respondents' choices which supports the high frequency occurrence of this theme.

Figure 49 peoples' preference for Natural and Man-made elements.

Researches support this result that access to natural elements can significantly improve mental well-being and provide a sense of restoration (Kaplan and Kaplan, 1989). natural elements made users feel relaxed and tend to spend time in those places was a conclusion of a study conducted by (Hollander et al., 2018). These results were also aligned with the outcomes of (Negami et al., 2018) who found that Urban design elements featuring greenery were associated with higher levels of happiness and attraction among participants.

5.5.1.2. Tranquility and relaxation

The connection between the natural environment and emotional well-being is highlighted in this theme, with 14.8% of the participants expressing feelings of calmness, relaxation, and stress relief when engaging with natural spaces. Statements like “A little tranquility amidst chaos” and “Mental relaxation and stress reduction,” support that natural settings provide a space for tranquility and relaxation.

Figure 50 Word cloud analysis for Tranquillity and Relaxation theme

The word cloud in Figure 50 shows that the words like “relax,” “Calm”, “tranquility”, “meditation”, “restful” and “peaceful” all have highly occurred in the responses this indicates the strong feeling of relaxation users perceived when watching the natural environment stimuli.

This reflects a desire for peaceful and quiet spaces within an urban environment free from congestion. Studies have shown that tranquil environments can enhance cognitive function and reduce anxiety (Ulrich, 2002). Creating serene spaces such as public spaces and pedestrian zones can help reduce stress and improve well-being. This theme underscores the value of designing urban spaces to enhance the emotional experience of residents and provide a peaceful refuge.

5.5.1.3. Aesthetic and social values

Respondents considerably valued the aesthetic and social aspects of natural settings, with 25.9% of mentions considering it an essential component. This underscores the need to create urban environments that are visually attractive and promote social interaction. Therefore, it is worth noting that nature offers spaces that combine both aesthetic and social value.

Figure 51 Word Cloud analysis for Aesthetic and Social value themes in natural urban environment

The word cloud in Figure 51 shows the frequency of word occurrence related to this theme, people highly perceived the aesthetic value of Natural environments by mentioning words like “Beautiful”, “nice”, “artistic”, and “Lovely”.

Supporting this result, (Lynch, 1964) claimed that the visual quality of the urban environment profoundly impacts individuals' perception and interaction with their surroundings. This finding suggests that urban planners and architects should incorporate further aesthetic and social considerations to promote community engagement and improve the overall quality of urban living.

5.5.1.4. Historical and Cultural Significance

This theme represents the cultural aspects people highlighted in the given image of the natural environment, which is valued by 12.3% of responses. It indicates an appreciation and value of historical elements within urban environments. This indicates that preserving

historical sites and integrating cultural elements into modern settings can enhance a sense of identity and cultural value for users.

Figure 52 Word cloud analysis for Historical and cultural significance theme

The word cloud in Figure 52 shows the high frequency of words like “Historical, Heritage, Traditional and Cultural” which indicates the perception of historical elements that occurred in the given stimuli. This highlights a link between nature and natural materials that respondents perceived frequently together as earlier occurred in their perception of the historical environment.

This result is supported by literature indicating the human natural initiation for the biophilic elements and historic elements are found in human roots and origin (Wilson, 1986, Sussman and Hollander, 2021). Supporting this result, (Tuan, 1977) emphasizes the importance of place and cultural heritage integration to enhance the overall human experience and attachment to places. This can create a narrative of space that connects past and present and enriches the urban experience of residents.

5.5.1.5. Cleanliness and maintenance

The theme was mentioned less commonly yet appeared in the responses, with a frequency of 2.5%. suggesting the importance of perceived cleanliness and well-maintained urban space is crucial for public well-being.

Word Cloud for Cleanliness and Maintenance

Figure 53 Word Cloud analysis for cleanliness and maintenance

Figure 53 shows that words like “Well-maintained, clean, organized, neat, and tidy” were perceived by respondents in the given stimuli. This can indicate that cleanliness and maintenance of space can positively impact human perception. This result is aligned with the results of (Eldridge, 2022) found that people were feeling happier, more relaxed, and less stressed in upkept spaces as compared to neglected or unorganized spaces.

This result indicated that regular maintenance and cleanliness can prevent the deterioration of urban spaces and enhance their usability and functionality. The implementation of effective maintenance strategies can keep public spaces clean and more welcoming and positively influence users’ perceptions.

5.5.1.6. Environmental Concerns, Suggestions for Improvement, Practical Uses

Participants mentioned environmental concerns with a frequency of 4.9% of responses, and suggestions for improving urban environments and practical uses were noted by 7.4% and 2.5%, respectively. These themes can reflect an awareness of sustainability issues and indicate that residents find potential for enhancement and practical application that aligns with residents’ needs.

Figure 54 Word cloud analysis for Suggestions of improvement, environmental concerns, and practical uses

The word clouds in Figure 54 highlight the three least-occurring themes, while still mentioning the concerns and suggestions perceived by the respondents. These themes' occurrence can highlight the importance of the participation of the residents in the planning process to better inform the decision-makers, designers, and planners of the needs and preferences of users.

Supporting this, (Gehl, 2010) has indicated that people's participation and suggestions for improving the planning process can lead to more effective and sustainable urban design solutions.

The results of this section highlight a diverse perception of Duhok city residents regarding the natural urban environment. "Natural Elements", "tranquility", "Aesthetic", "Historically significant" and "Social value" were perceived and significantly valued. Those elements, while integrated in designing urban environments, can enhance the overall well-being and experience of the users. This can create environments that are more livable, sustainable, and humane.

5.5.2. Emotional response toward natural environments

The emotional response to natural environments was assessed through a comprehensive visual analysis, as illustrated in the bar chart below. The chart illustrates the frequency of various emotional responses to natural settings.

Figure 55 Bar Chart representing emotions toward Natural Urban Environment

The majority of individuals expressed positive sentiments towards the natural environment in the study area. The highest number of reported as in Figure 55, (101) of responses were feeling joyful. relaxed (98) and interested (50). This suggests that the natural environment has a positive influence on well-being and human engagement. Individuals were experiencing a sense of pride and excitement, with 26 people feeling proud and 22 people feeling excited. This highlights the pleasant and restoring atmosphere of these areas aligning with the theory of restoration in natural settings by (Kaplan and Kaplan, 1989).

Figure 56 Radar Chart analysis, Representing the Emotional Quadrant in response to Natural Urban Environment

The radar charts presented in Figure 59 classify emotional responses into four quadrants: Calm-Pleasant, Energized-Pleasant, Energized-Unpleasant, and Calm-Unpleasant. The natural environment strongly demonstrated the Calm-Pleasant quadrant, which represents feelings of Joy, Relaxation, and Pride.

Figure 57 participants' response bar chart towards the benefit of nature

However, few people indicated the Energized-Pleasant quadrant, which represents a sense of Interest and Excitement. The data presented in Figure 57 demonstrates the substantial impact of nature on improving both mental and physical well-being. The respondents most commonly mentioned mental relaxation and stress reduction as the primary benefits of nature. Additionally, enhanced mood and emotional well-being were reported by a large percentage of individuals. However, only a minority of people found no benefits in nature.

The frequent mentions of mental relaxation, stress reduction, and enhanced mood highlighting strong sentiments toward the positive influence of nature suggest that urban planning should prioritize the integration and maintenance of green areas to create cities that are more conducive to the well-being of inhabitants. This finding is consistent with an earlier mentioned research by (Capineri et al., 2018) which showed that green areas are rated most positively, while heavily trafficked areas receive negative ratings from participants.

The positive correlation between man and the natural environment was observed in results that illustrated the dominance of positive emotional responses among participants; this outcome highlights the role of nature in promoting a sense of restoration and relaxation. The observation aligns with the results reported by (Negami et al., 2018) who discovered

that urban design elements such as increased greenery are associated with higher levels of happiness and engagement with the surroundings. Incorporating the visual aesthetic and improved functionality of urban space design.

The findings from this survey highlight the multifaceted benefits of green areas, emphasizing their importance in urban planning and the design of public spaces. To maximize these benefits, urban planners and policymakers should consider increasing green spaces to promote mental and physical health. In turn, enhancing accessibility to make green areas easily accessible to all residents, and incorporating natural elements into the design of public spaces, workplaces, and educational institutions. As a result, it potentially leads to enhanced mood, focus, and overall well-being, and encourages community engagement in the maintenance and design of green spaces to ensure they meet the needs and preferences of the residents. By understanding and leveraging the benefits of green areas, cities can create healthier, more vibrant, and more sustainable environments for their inhabitants.

5.6. Perception of narrative elements in urban built environments

Architects and urban planners may learn a lot about human behavior and the ways they seek meaning in their built environment, from structures to street layouts by studying storytelling.

As stated in Chapter 4, an extensive list of the main elements that form a city's narrative including monuments and sculptures, street names, historic structures, public art, and public spaces was presented. The narrative elements shown in Figure 61 were given as a checklist to the participants.

Figure 58 Narrative elements presented to Participants in the Questionnaire

The results indicated that respondents' preferences were highly consistent, as shown in Figure 58. indicating that certain urban elements were important to all the participants

regardless of their level of qualifications. In this perspective, rather than contributing to people's feelings of isolation and detachment, it is crucial to design spaces that respond to their basic requirements for a sense of belonging and meaning.

Figure 59 the participant's response to the main elements contributing to Narrativity

The data collected from the respondents indicates a distinct preference for specific elements in an urban setting. Historic buildings were considered the most significant in terms of contributing to the city's narrativity, with 29% of the total responses. Monuments and statues came in second place with a percentage of 26%. Parks and public spaces were valued by 20% of the participants, although they were not ranked as highly as historic buildings and monuments. Public art and street names were the least favored options for enhancing the narrativity of the city, with 13% and 11% respectively as shown in Figure 59. The analysis of the participants' responses underscores the significance of historical features, which are seen as highly important, closely followed by monuments and sculptures.

5.6.1. Enhancing Duhok's Urban Narrative Through Key Urban Elements

The participants were presented with urban features from the Duhok city center to determine how individuals perceive the elements that contribute to the city's storytelling. although it did not represent any historical events or the city's history. The findings revealed that historic buildings were among the most valued elements in the city's narrative, with 36% of mentions, exceeding other elements. Statues and monuments accounted for 21% of preferences, and 13% of the respondents expressed a preference for public art, specifically mosaic artwork portraying Kurdish women as a representation of

Kurdish culture. 10% of the respondents highlighted public spaces and parks. The least favored components included the "Duhok" letter statue, the outdoor amphitheater, and the metal monument symbolizing Nawroz as shown in Figure 60.

Figure 60 Participants' preference of the Narrative elements in the Duhok city study area

The analysis of data clearly shows that historic buildings are the cornerstone of creating Duhok city's urban narration, followed by statues and monuments and culturally represented public art. This result indicates the importance of those structures in representing the city's storytelling and narrativity as stated by Lynch (1960) and Rossi (1982). Arguably, stating the importance of preserving the city's heritage to provide people with an emotional connection to the past and embody the cultural, architectural, and historical characteristics. These buildings help to define and maintain the distinct identity of the city, provoking a sense of belonging among residents.

Furthermore, the significant perception of statues and monuments, although lacking any historical ties, shows the value of those elements within the urban context that gives value in enhancing the cultural and artistic narrativity of urban spaces and environments. The moderate preference for public parks and art also shows the importance of their contribution to the urban experiences of the residents which can promote community engagement and the aesthetic value of urban spaces.

5.6.2. Emotional response toward Narrative elements

This section examines the impact of urban narrative elements on the emotional reactions of individuals living in Duhok City. The elements are categorized into four quadrants

according to the PANAS wheel of emotions. This classification highlights the extent to which these factors impact the emotional connection between the urban environment and its residents.

When asked about their emotions towards the selected features in the Duhok urban context, the majority of respondents expressed positive emotions such as joy, pride, and excitement. The emotions most frequently reported, suggesting a significant level of engagement, were "Joyful" and "Interested". The existence of emotions such as pride and inspiration suggests a strong and meaningful relationship between the urban components and the cultural and historical character of the city. The prevalence of relaxed and excited responses suggests that the presence of these features in urban environments, as seen in Fig 61, creates a peaceful pleasant atmosphere.

Figure 61 Emotional response bar chart of Narrative urban elements

In contrast, infrequently reported negative feelings were overshadowed by an overwhelming amount of positive affective responses.

Figure 62 Emotional quadrants analysis of Narrative urban elements

The majority of the described feelings are concentrated in the "Calm-Pleasant" and "Energized-Pleasant" quadrants, as indicated by the PANAS wheel of emotions shown in Figure 62. Expressing a deep and positive emotional response, such as joy, satisfaction, relaxation, and inspiration, towards the urban elements of the city of Duhok. This implies that the citizens' sense of well-being and contentment are invoked through the narrative aspects of the city. By utilizing this data, urban planners may strengthen their ability to design urban environments that foster positive interaction and improve overall well-being.

5.7. Human City Model and Emotional Well-being

The urban environment has an important influence on the psychological well-being of its residents. To enhance the positive effects, a comprehensive approach to urban design is generated and incorporates three essential components: The natural environment and historic and narrative-built environments as shown in Figure 63. This comprehensive framework emphasizes the crucial need to integrate these elements in the design to promote psychological well-being and a feeling of communal identity.

The natural environment, which encompasses the design of green spaces, parks, and the preservation of natural landscapes, plays a crucial role in promoting both physical and emotional well-being. Access to nature has been demonstrated to minimize stress, enhance mood, and promote physical activity. The historic built environment aims to preserve architectural and cultural heritage, which includes landmarks and historical structures. By maintaining these components, urban areas can preserve their distinct character and enhance the feeling of belonging and attachment among inhabitants, consequently improving their emotional connection with the surrounding environments.

The narrative environment refers to the planned arrangement of storytelling elements within a city, encompassing its historical incidents, collective experiences, and cultural narratives, which collectively define the city's identity. Public arts, community events, and traditional practices can be incorporated as narrative components in urban developments to enhance the social fabric of urban life. Integrating these factors creates a convincing framework for urban planners and policymakers to use as recommendations for creating urban environments. As a result, this can create places that promote well-being while also enriching the city's cultural identity. This method seeks to develop more humane cities that promote a positive state of mind.

HUMAN CITY MODEL WHEEL FOR MENTAL WELL-BEING

Figure 63 Critical Components of a Human-Centered City: Developing a Framework for Psychological Well-Being in Urban Environments Source: Researcher constructed.

The Human City Model Wheel illustrates the interplay between the historic built environment, natural built environment, and narrative environment, emphasizing how these dimensions collectively enhance mental well-being. By balancing historical preservation, incorporating natural elements, and fostering community narratives through urban design, cities can effectively promote emotional health, social connectivity, and cultural identity, ultimately contributing to more human-centered and psychologically supportive urban spaces.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION

6. Overview

This chapter presents the key findings and conclusions of the research, offering a comprehensive understanding of how different urban environments influence human perception and emotional experiences. The research was conducted through a multidisciplinary lens; the study combined environmental psychology and urban planning theories with insights from literature and recent studies. It also provides recommendations for urban planning and design based on the study's outcomes.

The research explored the impact of urban design elements on the emotions and perceptions of Duhok City residents, focusing on elements that positively contribute to human experiences within urban spaces. By adopting a human-centered approach and using mixed methods of data collection and analysis, the study identified key factors influencing the human state of mind. These elements were historical, narrative, and natural. Built environmental features were highlighted due to their strong positive influence, further analyzed and measured within the context of Duhok City. The findings emphasized that perception and emotional responses to the built environment vary based on cultural context and personal experiences.

The study revealed that Duhok City's urban planning has prioritized vehicle movement over human-scale design, leading to a lack of pedestrian-friendly environments, green spaces, and climate-responsive design. Findings emphasized the importance of integrating historical, narrative, and natural elements into new urban developments to create more engaging and human-centered spaces. Through an interdisciplinary approach, the study demonstrated that well-planned urban environments positively impact the human state of mind.

Data collected through interviews, field observations, document reviews, and questionnaires reinforced the need to incorporate historical elements, nature-inspired design, and storytelling aspects into urban planning. Prioritizing people in the design process allows urban planners, architects, and policymakers to develop vibrant and emotionally enriched spaces that strengthen the connection between people and their surroundings.

Ultimately, the research highlights the significance of a human-centered approach in urban planning—one that moves beyond functionality to prioritize well-being, livability, and sustainability. Creating thoughtful, responsive urban spaces ensures a positive emotional experience for residents, fostering a deeper connection between people and the built environment.

6.1. Addressing Research Questions and Objectives

This research has addressed its objectives by establishing a strong correlation between built environment elements and Mental well-being, emphasizing the role of historical, narrative, and natural environmental elements in shaping human experiences within urban spaces as follows:

- A mixed-method approach through a semi-structured questionnaire has provided empirical evidence that key design elements such as Historic sites, Natural features, and Narrative elements of the built environment significantly have a positive impact on the human state of mind.
- The study revealed that perception and emotions are not passive reactions to the built environment but rather an active interaction that shapes the way people experience their surroundings.
- Duhok City residents' perceptual and emotional responses were analyzed using thematic analysis, word clouds, and the PANAS wheel of emotions, highlighting that historical, natural, and narrative elements consistently evoke positive emotional responses.
- The findings emphasize the importance of human-environment interaction in creating more humanized urban spaces, reinforcing that functionality alone is not enough, psychological well-being must be considered in urban planning and development.
- The research aligns with Maslow's hierarchy of needs and Carl Rogers' humanistic approach, stressing that the built environment should not only serve functional purposes but also respond to deeper psychological and emotional needs.

- The study contributed to the development of a human-city model, identifying key physical and sub-elements that should be integrated into future urban design and planning to foster a more thoughtful and emotionally supportive built environment.
- Ultimately, this research provides an understanding of how a holistic approach that integrates emotional well-being, Historical identity, and biophilic design can transform urban spaces into environments that enhance the human experience.

6.2. The influence of built Environment elements on human state of mind

- **Historic elements** of the built environment contribute to positive emotional experiences, fostering a sense of place, identity, and community pride. Their preservation and integration in future urban developments can enhance the quality of urban spaces and people's experience.
- **Natural elements** such as water features, greenery, and natural materials (specifically "stone" in the Kurdish context) were frequently associated with positive emotions. This highlights their significant influence on perception and their role in enhancing relaxation and reducing stress when people are exposed to nature.
- **Narrative elements**, though less explored in literature, were highly valued by participants in the Duhok city context, contributing to more engaging and meaningful urban spaces. This underscores their potential to create a new system of relationships between users and urban spaces that form deeper emotional connections within the built environment. They can perceive the stories behind the city's history and cultural identity through elements like Monuments, statues, public art, materials, and colors used in the space design.

These elements play a crucial role in enhancing human-environment interaction, which is essential for rehumanizing urban space design. Aligning with UNESCO's global call for City Humanization, this approach supports the development of a humanizing model that prioritizes psychological well-being, shifting the focus beyond economic, physical, and social aspects of urban planning.

- **Emotional Response**

Emotions can refer to the outcomes of human perception, whether negative or positive responses. When Perceptions are translated into emotions, they can range from Joy and excitement to stress and frustration. For instance, a well-designed Urban environment may evoke relaxation and Joy, whereas a chaotic urban setting may trigger anxiety or discomfort. This highlights the importance of biophilic design, Historic environments, and storytelling elements in fostering positive emotional experiences.

- **Behavioral Outcomes**

Behavior refers to the way humans act or respond to their environment, influenced by their perceptions and emotions. It includes actions, interactions, and decisions in different contexts, such as social engagement, movement, walking, cycling, and daily routine activities.

Emotions influence behaviors, shaping how individuals interact with their environment. A walkable, engaging, and aesthetically pleasing cityscape encourages active lifestyles, social interactions, and a sense of attachment. In contrast, environments perceived as uninviting or stressful lead to avoidance behaviors, reduced social interactions, and increased reliance on cars over pedestrian movement.

The Cycle Continues behavior, in turn, reinforces perception, completing the cycle. A city designed with human-centered principles creates a positive feedback loop, enhancing perceptions, emotions, and behaviors over time. Conversely, poor urban planning results in negative experiences, leading to disconnection and dissatisfaction among residents.

Urban design is not just about functionality but also about fostering positive human experiences. A well-planned city promotes engagement, active lifestyles, and community well-being, reinforcing a positive behavioral cycle. Ignoring human-centered design leads to negative perceptions, emotional distress, and disengagement from Urban spaces.

This model serves as a foundation for future urban policies and planning strategies, advocating for a more responsive, inclusive, and psychologically supportive built environment.

6.4. Recommendations

Based on the research findings and results, several recommendations can be suggested to improve urban planning and design practices for future urban developments in Duhok City:

6.4.1. Prioritization of Historic Site Conservation

Urban planning policies and strategical plans should consider the importance of preserving Historic Urban Environments, while also adapting and integrating the cultural and built heritage elements in future developments to better enhance and enrich the identity of Duhok City while considering it as a crucial aspect in enhancing human well-being, this can lead to more humanized urban environment and spaces.

6.4.2. Enhancing Biophilic Design Integration in City

Duhok City residents expressed dissatisfaction with the amount of greenery and green areas, this is a call for investing more in green infrastructures like parks, urban open spaces, and green areas. The natural elements should be strategically distributed and considered in City planning to ensure better access to nature and enhance human well-being.

6.4.3. Integration of narrative elements

Storytelling and narrative elements like monuments, historic structures, street names, public arts, and the reflection of storytelling of the place in Design and Planning strategies can enhance the quality of urban space design and the cognitive process of users. This can lead to more humanized environments.

In general, well-designed and thoughtful planning can enhance the Human-Environment interaction, which can generate a more Humanized city in terms of Human psychological well-being and attachment.

6.5. Implications for Education and curriculum development

The incorporation of design and well-being materials or Environmental psychology and interdisciplinary academic fields in educational programs is essential to the learning process in sectors such as interior design, Architecture, urban planning, and design

curricula. Educators can better prepare students for more thoughtful design and planning to enhance and promote psychological experience and human interactions with spaces.

This approach can ensure that future professionals have better knowledge about designing cities and places that contribute to human needs and promote overall quality of life.

6.6. Future work and research

This study has provided an intensive literature review of the crucial human-centered design aspects, related psychological and planning theories, and human-centric approaches. It further explored the design elements and urban planning dimensions that play an important role in enhancing human well-being within urban spaces. Building upon the findings of this study, there are several suggestions and guidelines for considering the importance of interdisciplinary research, specifically in Environmental psychology and its integration into Architecture, urban design, and planning. To better engage and understand the cultural and psychological aspects while planning for future developments.

- Assessing other design elements highlighted in this research contributes to Psychological and social well-being.
- Inclusivity in assessment, while considering the study of perception and emotional experience among other age groups that the study did not cover, further comparison between both genders' perceptions.
- Expanding the geographical scope of Urban and Rural comparison provides a more comprehensive understanding. Comparative studies from different cultures, cities, and environmental contexts can add invaluable insights.
- Utilizing New technology tools integration, like Virtual reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR), lab settings, and psychological state evaluation tools like EEG, eye-tracking, heart rate measurements, and other advancements highlighted in the study while studying this correlation between urban design and human well-being to mitigate the limitations of self-reporting classic tools.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A (Questionnaire sample)

Questionnaire on The Impact of Built Environment on Human state of mind - Duhok

This questionnaire seeks to understand how urban environments affect individuals' preferences and well-being. Your feedback will help us comprehend this impact and help us improve and design better urban spaces.

Instructions:

- Every response should be collected immediately after viewing each image to ensure that emotional responses and preferences are accurately captured.
- This survey should take approximately 10-15 minutes to complete.

Demographic Information

- Gender
 - Male
 - Female
- Educational Level
 - High school or equivalent
 - Bachelor's degree
 - Master's degree
 - Doctorate
 - Other (please specify): _____
- Educational background
 - Architectural Engineering
 - Spatial/Urban Planning
 - Psychology
 - Other...
- Age Group
 - 20-24
 - 25-29
 - 30-34
 -

Section 1 Historic Urban Environment

This section explores how different urban environments affect our perceptions and emotions.

1.1. How would you describe this picture? Please mention any specific details that stand out to you.

1.2. How do you feel when you see the picture? (You can choose more than one Emotion)

- Question type
- Joyful
- Interested
- Proud
- Excited
- Inspired
- Relaxed
- Stressed
- Upset
- Frustrated
- Scared
- Ashamed
- others

1.3. Rate how much you agree with the statement: "Historical buildings and environments contribute to human mental well-being."

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 Strongly Agree

Section 2: Natural Urban Environment

2.1. What benefits do you receive from areas with natural elements " Green Areas"? (Select all that apply)

Physical health improvement

- Mental relaxation and stress reduction
- Enhanced mood and emotional well-being
- Increased focus and concentration
- None
- Other: _____

2.2. How would you describe this picture? Please mention any specific details that stand out to you.

2.3. How do you feel when you see the picture? (You can choose more than one Emotion)

- Joyful
- Interested
- Proud
- Excited
- Inspired
- Relaxed
- Stressed
- Upset
- Frustrated
- Scared
- Ashamed
- Other...

2.4. Which group do you prefer: A (3 photos on the left) or B (3 photos on the right)?

- A
- B

Section 3: Narrativity

This section explores how different structures in the city tell stories and convey messages through their design.

3.1. Which of the following elements do you think best contribute to the **storytelling of the city's history**? (You can choose more than one)

Monuments and statues

Historic buildings

Parks and public spaces

Street names

Public art

3.2. Which of the following structures do you find most aesthetically pleasing?

- A) Colorful wall and staircase with cafe
- B) 'Duhok' sign with red heart
- C) Traditional stone building with red brick wall
- D) Stone building with wooden door
- E) Open-air amphitheater
- F) Mosaic wall art
- G) Stone statue of a man
- H) Stone statue of a woman
- I) Metal monument representing Newroz

3.3. Please describe your emotional response to the structure you selected? (You can choose more than one)

- Joyful
- Interested
- Proud
- Excited
- Inspired
- Relaxed
- Stressed
- Upset
- Frustrated
- Scared
- Ashamed
- Other

Final Notes: Do you have any additional comments or suggestions regarding the urban environment of Duhok city center?

Long-answer text

**Kurdistan Region of Iraq
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**Measurement of Emotional and Perceptual Responses in Urban Environments:
Experts Validation and Consensus Report**

Abstract

This study explores the impact of urban design elements, particularly heritage and biophilia, and narratives on residents' emotional states and experiences in Duhok, using quantitative and qualitative methods to establish a validated emotional response scale. This research aims to measure emotional and perceptual responses from built environment design, assessing its impact on residents' emotional well-being and understanding the interaction between the built environment and human emotions.

Methodology

1. Emotional Response Scale

The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) was chosen as the primary tool for assessing emotional responses and measuring positive and negative affect through self-report items. Participants will be presented with images of urban settings and asked to report their emotions. PANAS as shown in Figure (1) is chosen for its ability to distinguish positive and negative affective states and allows participants to report multiple emotions simultaneously, aligning with the study's goal of understanding emotional responses triggered by diverse urban environments.

Relevant emotions in built environments as shown in Table (1) include joy, pride, stress, and inspiration. Positive emotions are linked to well-designed, culturally resonant spaces, while negative emotions like stress or fear stem from poor design or danger. Tools like PANAS measure these emotional responses, helping planners and architects design environments that evoke positive emotions while mitigating negative ones.

Table 1 : Emotions Triggered by Visual Stimuli in Built Environments

Joyful	Associated with spaces promoting leisure, beauty, and social interaction. (Li et al., 2022)
Relaxed	Tied to environments featuring natural elements. (Grahm et al., 2010)
Excited	Spaces that evoke a sense of novelty, and engagement (Wagener et al., 2022)
Stressed	Triggered by overcrowded, noisy, or visually cluttered spaces.(Gatersleben et al., 2017)
Upset/Frustrated	Arise in environments that feel uncomfortable, and inaccessible. (Ellin, 1997)
Ashamed	associated with feelings of disrepair or neglect. (Weijis-Perrée et al., 2020)
Scared	Elicited by environments that feel unsafe due to poor lighting, isolation, and visible danger. (Burns, 2000)
Proud	spaces that reflect cultural or community identity (Knez et al., 2018)
Inspired	Triggered by aesthetically beautiful or innovative design. (Desai and Psychology, 2024)
Interest	Often sparked by unique, innovative, or culturally significant spaces. (Dzebic, 2018)

1.2. How do you feel when you see the picture? (You can choose more than one feeling)

- Joyful
- Interested
- Proud
- Excited
- Inspired
- Relaxed
- Stressed
- Upset
- Frustrated
- Scared
- Ashamed
- Add option or Add "Other"

The emotions will be analyzed into four quadrants as shown in Table (2), each quadrant includes a group of emotions that demonstrate a specific behavioral response or human state:

- **Calm-Unpleasant:** Identifies lack of engagement and vibrant environment, often found in urban spaces lacking human dimensions.
- **Energized-Unpleasant:** Describes spaces lacking social control, creating tension and discomfort, often leading to unwanted behaviors.
- **Calm-Pleasant:** Stimulates pleasant but low-energy emotions, often found in tranquil environments like green parks or quiet spaces.
- **Energized-Pleasant:** Represents vibrant and engaging urban spaces, promoting positive emotional experiences and enhancing social interaction.

Table 2 : Related quadrants according to PANAS:

Quadrant	Emotions
Calm-Pleasant	Joyful, Proud, Inspired, Relaxed
Energized-Pleasant	Interested, Excited
Energized-Unpleasant	Stressed, Upset, Frustrated
Calm-Unpleasant	Scared, Ashamed

Figure 1 : Representing Wheel of emotions (Brdar, 2020)

The analysis of emotions and emotional quadrants shall be represented as shown in the below figures (2,3).

Figure 2: Bar chart representing the frequency of emotions. emotional response

Figure 3: Radar Chart representing Quadrant of

2. Perceptual Response Measurement

The study used open-ended questions to gather residents' perceptions of urban spaces, identifying design elements and impressions. Thematic analysis identified recurring themes related to architecture, cultural symbolism, nature, and human-environment interaction, highlighting the importance of understanding how perceptual experiences shape emotional reactions and contribute to the humanization of public spaces.

1.1. How would you describe this picture? Please mention any specific details that stand out to you. What comes to mind when you think about our brand

Expert Review and Validation

The Scale of measurement selected will undergo validation by psychology and psychiatry experts to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the emotional and perceptual response measurement and analysis tools used in evaluating the impacts of the urban built environment on the participant's emotions and perceptual experience.

Long-answer text

Name:

Academic Title:

Affiliation:

Signature: _____

Date: _____

حكومهتا ههريما كوردستاني - عيراق
وهزارهتا خویندنا بالا و تونینهوهیا زانستی
زانكویا دهوك
كولیرا پلانسازیا شار و ههريمان
بهشی پلاندانانا جهی

روخساری مروقاتیکرنا باژیران: پیقانا کارتیکرنا ژینگهها ئافاکری ل سهر باری دهروونی پی مروقی

ئهف تیزه هاتیه پیشکیش کرن بو جفاتا کولیرا پلانسازیا شار و ههريمان – زانكویا دهوك وهك مهرجه کی ب جهئینانا
بروانامهیا ماستهري د بیاف پلاندانانا جهی دا

ژلا پی:

بهیبین جلادت مصطفی البیبونی

ل ژیر سهرپه رشتیا:

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